

**CULTURAL NORMS AND CHILDCARE PRACTICES IN
SELECTED LOW-INCOME URBAN COMMUNITIES IN
ALIMOSHO LGA, LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA.**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this work, "**Impact of Cultural Norms on Responsive Childcare Practices in Select Low-Income Urban Communities In Alimosho LGA, Lagos State, Nigeria**" was carried out by Akinboboye, Pamela Chioma, Reg. number (20234000689) in partial fulfillment for the award of the degree of M.Sc. in Sustainable Social Development, Centre of Excellence in Sustainable Procurement, Environmental and Social Standards (CE-sPESS), Federal University Of Technology, Owerri.

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to the vibrant and resilient children of Nigeria. May this work serve as a beacon of hope and a catalyst for positive change in early childhood development.

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ABSTRACT

The lack of a comprehensive understanding regarding how norms of childcare influence infant-toddler caregiving practices is identified as a major problem within low-income urban communities. Recognizing the critical importance of the first three years of life for cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development, the thesis investigated the interplay of cultural childcare norms, economic factors, and caregiving practices in shaping infant-toddler development within low-income urban communities in Alimosho Local Government Area (LGA), Lagos, Nigeria. It emphasized the role of responsive caregiving as a cornerstone for optimal child development. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative surveys (n=89), in-dept-interviews(n=8), focus group discussions(n=7), and direct caregiver-child observations. The study population included mothers and other caregivers in three Local Council Development Areas (LCDAs) within Alimosho LGA. Qualitative findings from semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions elucidated the cultural childcare norms influencing caregiving behaviors. Almost half of the respondents (48.3%) reported that cultural norms had a moderate to strong influence on caregiving. Caregivers expressed a strong belief in the benefits of traditional practices such as massaging and communal child rearing aiding relaxation and proper development. The compounded challenges faced by caregivers were revealed to be due to economic realities, including limited income and access to quality childcare services. Of the respondents, 51.7% believed that poverty significantly impacted their caregiving and cultural expectations surrounding childcare also appeared to be influenced by financial constraints as 32.6% acknowledged that cultural expectations about childcare changed depending on costs. The study's hypothesis (H2)—that there is no significant association between caregiver-child interaction behaviors and child engagement—was rejected as results showed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.692$, $p < 0.001$) underscoring the importance of responsive caregiving in shaping immediate child engagement and emotional responses. Inferential statistical analysis also demonstrated a significant relationship between type of childcare provider and cultural caregiving preferences. Generally, findings of the study underscore the importance of social support networks and the role of paid childcare services in facilitating responsive caregiving. The findings contribute to Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 1, 3, 4, 5, and 10 by highlighting the importance of culturally sensitive early childhood interventions that address both traditional caregiving practices and contemporary economic challenges.

Keywords: Responsive caregiving, cultural norms, early childhood development, Alimosho LGA, Nigeria, Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological Theory.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Study Background

The first three years of life are a fertile ground for shaping a child's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical trajectory. Genetic predispositions (nature) interact with environmental influences (nurture) to shape lifelong outcomes. A major nurture influence, which are caregiving practices are expected to have profound positive impact where they are responsive. Responsive caregiving, characterized by warmth, sensitivity, and attuned responses to a child's needs, is recognized as a cornerstone of optimal development during the critical periods of child development. However, in low-income urban communities, providing responsive caregiving is immensely affected by the intricate interplay of cultural caregiving norms, economic realities, and available support networks.

The context motivating this study is multifaceted. Early childhood development has become a global public health priority, as the Global Sustainable Development Goals 1 through 4 have implications for learning, health, and well-being and strong interest exists in many countries and in the global community to move beyond child survival to protect and support optimal child development, which is especially urgent for children less than 5 years old at risk of failing to achieve their potential. Yet, within low-income urban communities, these priorities are often overshadowed by the harsh realities of poverty, limited access to resources, and social stressors. These factors can significantly impact child development outcomes, making responsive caregiving even more crucial.

Cultural norms are the shared beliefs, values, and behaviors that shape human existence and the evolution of culture. They influence our perception of reality and play a role in determining how individuals and societies function (Gelfand & Jackson, 2016). Cultural norms influence all areas of communal living including parenting and childcare practices which is a critical focus in this study. It offer a unique lens through which families navigate the complexities of childrearing. Nigeria's diverse cultural landscape, with its numerous ethnic groups, each has unique child-rearing rules and practices that are transmitted across generations. The Nigerian cultural context places a high value on children, viewing them as links between the past, present, and future. This perspective fosters a nurturing environment where children receive affection, stimulation, and support from multiple caregivers, which

contributes to their overall development. Community involvement in child-rearing emphasizes that caregiving is a shared responsibility among family members and even the broader community. This communal caregiving approach fosters a supportive environment for children, where multiple caregivers contribute to their upbringing. Common cultural caregiving practices exist, such as where a complete “stranger” is expected to adjust the head of a baby aright on their mother’s back. Also, the same logic obliges an adult to discipline errant behaviors. Moreso, the home, as the custodian of cultural values, plays a crucial role in a child's early life. It is the primary socialization agent, where a child first forms relationships and learns essential knowledge, character, and social virtues. Each home, with its unique values and practices, profoundly influences child-rearing, shaping the psychological and social development of the growing child.

Unfortunately, cultural values emphasizing obedience, compliance and disciplinary techniques may often times stifle potential for responsiveness during caregiving even for very young children. Cultural childrearing norms in Nigeria often accept harsh disciplining methods, such as excessive spanking and corporal punishment. When there is a perceived mistake by children, they are looked at disdainfully, jeered at, or spanked, regardless of age, and sometimes in abusive manners. These practices are viewed as acceptable forms of discipline, despite being detrimental to a child's emotional and psychological well-being.

Responsive caregiving is a caregiving style that involves responding promptly and appropriately to a child's needs and signals. This type of caregiving is characterized by sensitivity, warmth, and responsiveness to the child's cues and is linked to improved psychosocial, cognitive, and physical outcomes in children (Scherer et al., 2019). Expressions of responsive caregiving across cultures differ significantly. In Euro-American middle-class culture, infants are typically raised in nuclear families, with the mother as the primary caregiver who frequently engages in face-to-face interaction with the child reading body cues and addressing infants' needs before they lead to overt negative expressions. However, responsive caregiving in several non-western communities are not limited to mothers but is a shared responsibility among caregivers in the community. The study of the Aka foragers highlights that both mothers and non-maternal caregivers (alloparents) show similar latency times in responding to infant distress (Mesman et al., 2018). Common baby-wearing practice common to many African cultures including Nigeria, reveals a display of responsiveness in a unique way where the caregiver uses close physical contact and rhythmic movements to help calm their babies, paying special attention

to the infant's emotional state helping them regulate their emotions by warmth and connection through touch and movement (Lavelli, Carra, Rossi, & Keller, 2019). Unfortunately, the bulk of research on caregiver-sensitive responsiveness has been carried out in parents as primary caregivers in Western countries and urban areas, and studies in non-Western rural regions, where extensive shared caregiving is the norm, are very rare.

Even within a single community, cultural childcare norms are not rigid. Research by Nsamenang (Greenfield & Cocking, 2014) in Cameroon highlighted the diverse interpretations of discipline among different ethnic groups. While some groups emphasized physical punishment, others focused on verbal reprimands or social disapproval. Cultural childcare norms are also not static but are transmitted across generations through socialization practices and family dynamics. Grandparents as key figures in transmitting child rearing practices, including culturally specific approaches to discipline and emotional support. However, in the vibrant tapestry of low-income urban communities, such pathways may experience modifications and mixtures from external cultures. Understanding these transmission pathways and changes are crucial for designing interventions that acknowledge and respect existing cultural practices while promoting practices that support optimal child development.

Rapid urbanization and population growth in Africa, coupled with the complex interplay between changing demographics, have resulted in significant implications for families. The influx of people into cities has led to the emergence of many slum communities and informal housing, characterized by overcrowding and limited access to basic services. This situation negatively impacts families' quality of life, increasing social inequality and poverty, and the persistent hold of poverty in many of these communities casts long shadows on responsive caregiving. Many families with low incomes experience childcare instability that has negative implications for both parental employment and children's development (Pilarz, Sandstrom, & Henly, 2022). Lagos state, although one of the largest urban agglomerations in the world, faces great challenges that have severe negative implications for childcare standards and by implication child development outcomes. According to reports from the World Bank Group, there are several housing and infrastructural challenges. There is a significant housing deficit of approximately 3.3 million units, with a large portion of the population living in informal housing. Only 35% of the population has access to public water supply, and only 5% is connected to the public sewerage system. Poor waste management, with a waste collection rate of only 20-30% and significant issues with recycling, high risk of flooding and coastal erosion resulting in

environmental vulnerabilities and inadequate sanitation facilities and public health services, contributing to poor living conditions (World Bank Group & Sustainable Urban and Regional Development, 2023). Coupled with all this is economic stagnation and high poverty rates, limited job opportunities and economic activities, particularly for women in lower-income areas, who face barriers to education, employment, and healthcare, which impacts their overall well-being and that of their families. The impact of these challenges hit hard on high-density areas like Alimosho, which is the selected location for our study.

In the midst of poverty, social support networks offer vital anchors. Extended family, neighbors, and community groups can provide emotional and practical support, sharing childcare responsibilities, offering respite, and alleviating some of the financial burdens on caregivers. According to the Lagos state household survey report (2021), Lagos West, where Alimosho LGA is located, childcare is the highest need of households; about 16% rely on neighbors. However, these networks can also be strained by poverty, with competing needs and limited resources. With the rate of rapid urbanization changing patterns of work, social structures, and gender norms, parents, mainly mothers, in low-income communities work long hours for insecure daily wages and depend on, childcare centers that have sprung up in informal settlements. However, there is currently little or no support to ensure they provide safe, nurturing care accessible to low-income families (Oloo et al., 2023). Additionally, cultural norms and expectations within these networks can sometimes clash with recommended caregiving practices, creating further challenges for families to responsive care.

Paid childcare services and early childhood education programs offer a potential lifeline for families seeking childcare support. According to the Lagos State Household Survey Report (2021), Alimosho LGA has 43% of children enrolled in pre-primary education, which was the highest reported percent of enrolled age group across the levels of education and across the 3 regions within the state. However, Paid childcare services and early childhood education programs (ECEs) in low-income urban communities in Lagos, encounter a myriad of economic challenges that impede their accessibility and effectiveness. Low-income families in Nigeria often face significant barriers to accessing affordable childcare. Paid childcare services are beyond the financial reach of many, and the limited number of formal childcare centers leads to overcrowded and substandard care (Casanova, Kabugi, & Udechukwu, 2023; World Bank Group & Sustainable Urban and Regional Development, 2023).

Quality is also an issue, as many informal daycare settings lack properly trained caregivers, which can impact the overall standard of care. Formal childcare centers often struggle with inadequate infrastructure and resources, limiting children's learning opportunities. Furthermore, the absence of effective regulation and government oversight compromises the safety and well-being of children in informal care. Social and cultural factors also play a role, with some families relying on traditional extended family care, and others avoiding formal services due to stigma and negative perceptions.

Poverty and unemployment within families affect their ability to afford or prioritize childcare services. Low-income parents face additional barriers to accessing childcare, including limited availability of care during nontraditional hours, limited availability of care for children with special needs, and limited availability of care in rural areas (Adams, Derrick-Mills, & Heller, 2016). Furthermore, the cultural appropriateness and sensitivity of these programs are crucial for ensuring their effectiveness. Finally, quality childcare is compromised in low-income settings where access to nutritious food and healthcare is limited due to results of high under-five mortality rates and the prevalence of stunting and protracted armed conflict, banditry, and farmer-herder violence have displaced millions of children and families, contributing to a loss of livelihood and educational opportunities (UNICEF, 2023).

Alimosho Local Government Area, situated in Lagos state, is the most densely populated and one of the lowest-income settlements within the state. With a projected population of over three million in 2019, this locality has a significant number of urban poor households engaged in the informal economic sector. Within Alimosho LGA, there are six Local Council Development Areas (LCDAs), each comprising a mix of small and large settlements. Among them, Agbado Oke-Odo, Ipaja-Ayobo and Mosan Okunola LCDAs are the focus of our research study.

The intricate interplay between cultural childcare norms, economic realities, and caregiving support networks, using Alimosho LGA as a case study warrants closer examination, particularly in light of potential consequences for child development. Examining the impact of cultural childcare norms on infant-toddler responsive caregiving in such low-income urban communities requires a multifaceted approach.

1.2. Problem Statement

The lack of a comprehensive understanding regarding how norms of childcare influence infant-toddler caregiving practices is identified as a major problem. Therefore, promoting responsive caregiving during the first three years of a child's life in low-income urban communities in Alimosho LGA, Lagos, Nigeria, is a challenge shaped by such cultural norms, economic realities, caregiver support and child development needs:

- Diverse and dynamic cultural childcare norms in urban landscapes, introduce complexities in expressing responsive caregiving.
- The transmission pathways of cultural caregiving practices within low-income urban communities is insufficiently explored, causing a gap in interventions that acknowledge and respect existing cultural practices while promoting those conducive to optimal child development.
- Economic challenges, unqualified caregivers, inadequate learning environments, and the lack of regulation compromise the quality of available childcare options. Also, tensions between traditional practices, gender expectations, and the stigma associated with formal childcare contribute to the complexity of caregiving decisions.
- Cultural caregiving practices intricately shape cognitive, social and emotional immediate responses and development, yet there is a limited exploration of how the norms governing these practices impact specific domains of child development within low-income urban communities.

Finally, there is paucity of comprehensive approach that moves beyond deficit perspectives to embrace the strengths and complexities inherent in low-income urban communities to design relevant interventions that promote optimal child development.

1.3. Main Objective

The aim of this study is to comprehensively investigate the impact of cultural childcare norms on infant-toddler responsive caregiving in low-income urban communities, using selected communities in Alimosho LGA as a case study.

1.4. Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this study include, to;

1. identify and examine the specific ways in which cultural childcare norms shape infant-toddler responsive caregiving practices within low-income urban communities.
2. assess the immediate effect of culturally influenced caregiving practices on infant-toddler development domains within low-income urban communities.
3. investigate how economic factors interact with and modify the influence of cultural norms on caregiving practices.
4. analyze the role of social support networks and Paid childcare services in mediating or moderating the relationship between cultural norms, economic realities, and responsive caregiving practices.

1.5. Hypotheses:

1. **Hypothesis (H1):** There is no significant influence of cultural norms within select low-income urban communities in Lagos, Nigeria on how (infant-toddler) caregiving practices express responsiveness.
 - a. **Hypothesis (H2):** There is no significant association between caregiver-child interaction behaviours and child engagement and emotional responses during caregiver interaction.
 - b. **Hypothesis (H3):** There is no significant association between selected sociodemographic characteristics (type of childcare facility, position at the facility) and cultural influence on childcare practices.

1.6. Justification for the Study

This research has the potential to directly improve the quality of care and child development outcomes in low-income urban communities. Recommendations from the study has potential to guide researchers, policymakers, childcare providers, and community leaders in tailoring interventions and services to specific cultural contexts and needs. This study makes significant contributions to several areas:

1. **Child Development:** By understanding the complex interplay between cultural norms, economic realities, and responsive caregiving, this study provides valuable insights into promoting optimal child development in low-income urban communities. This knowledge can be used to develop culturally sensitive interventions that support and strengthen responsive caregiving practices, leading to improved cognitive, social, emotional, and physical outcomes for children.
2. **Cultural Sensitivity:** This study challenges deficit perspectives and highlight the strengths and complexities inherent in diverse cultural caregiving practices. By fostering a deeper understanding of how cultural norms influence caregiving, this study promotes culturally sensitive approaches to interventions and policy development.
3. **Policy Development:** The findings of this study are crucial for informing the development of effective and culturally sensitive policies and programs aimed at supporting families and caregivers in low-income urban communities. This can include initiatives to address poverty, improve access to resources and Paid childcare services, and strengthen social support networks.
4. **Knowledge Gaps:** This study addresses a significant gap in the research literature on the impact of cultural norms on responsive caregiving in low-income urban communities, particularly in the context of Lagos, Nigeria. This knowledge contributes to a broader understanding of child development within diverse cultural contexts and informs future research efforts.

1.7. Scope of the Study

This research spanning a maximum duration of eight months, addressing the critical care influencers for children aged birth to three, adopts an interdisciplinary approach, integrating perspectives from developmental psychology, early childhood education, cultural anthropology, and social policy to examine how cultural norms shape caregiving behaviors and their effects on infant-toddler development. The study is conducted in Alimosho LGA, the most populous local government area in Lagos State, Nigeria. Alimosho is a rapidly urbanizing region with a mix of traditional and modern caregiving practices influenced by diverse cultural backgrounds, economic constraints, and shifting social structures. Specifically, the study focuses on three Local Council Development Areas (LCDAs) within Alimosho LGA- Agbado Oke-Odo, Ipaja-Ayobo, and Mosan Okunola LCDA's. These areas were selected due to their high concentration of low-income households, diverse ethnic composition, and prevalence of informal childcare arrangements, which provide a rich context for examining the interaction between cultural childcare norms, responsive caregiving, and support networks and paid childcare on child development outcomes.

The study primarily engages:

- **Primary caregivers:** Mothers, or an individual identified as the primary caregiver.
- **Paid childcare providers:** Home-based childcare providers, and Center-based childcare providers (crèches and nurseries)
- **Social support networks:** Relatives, friends, neighbors and religious center childcare support.

By focusing on Alimosho LGA, the research provides localized insights into urban childcare dynamics while also contributing to broader discussions on early childhood development in low-income settings within Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Review of Literature

Ensuring that children grow up in a stable environment that nurtures and promotes their health, nutritional, and developmental needs while protecting them from threats and providing them with interactions that are responsive, emotionally supportive, and stimulating is a key priority for promoting health across the lifespan (Ahun, Aboud, Wamboldt, & Yousafzai, 2023). The impact of cultural norms on infant-toddler-responsive childcare practices in low-income urban communities is an issue that has not been widely researched and requires a deeper understanding of the interplay between cultural values, economic realities, support structures, and caregiving practices that ultimately influence child development outcomes. This literature review encompasses a comprehensive examination of studies conducted over the past fifteen years. In review of previous research work capturing the various variables this study addresses, key topic areas will be explored:

2.1.1. Cultural Norms and Childcare Practices

The child's home is viewed as a crucial environment for socialization, where children learn moral behaviours and cultural values. The home serves as a "nursery bed" for nurturing these values, providing informal education and shaping personality development (Nwoke, 2013). Cultural norms are the shared expectations and rules that guide the behavior of people within social groups, learned and reinforced from parents, friends, teachers, and others while growing up in a society (Gelfand et al., 2011). These norms can be explicit or implicit, and they vary widely across different cultures (Savani, Morris, Fincher, Lu, & Kaufman, 2022). There are several of these explicit and especially implicit cultural norms that exert a profound influence on how infants and toddlers are cared for, nurtured, and socialized. For example, in many cultures, co-sleeping (sharing a bed with the child) is an explicit norm, often rooted in cultural beliefs about protection, bonding, and breastfeeding. However, in Western cultures, solitary sleep is increasingly promoted, often due to safety concerns (Yang & Wang, 2019). On the other hand, the level of physical closeness between caregiver and child is influenced by

implicit cultural beliefs about independence, dependence, and bodily autonomy. For instance, cultures that prioritize independence may encourage less physical closeness, promoting self-reliance in children, while those that value dependence may foster more intimate, responsive caregiving practices (Barnett, Hansen, Bailes, & Humphreys, 2022)

Culture influences caregiver cognitions that in turn shape caregiving practices and cultural goals related to desired developmental outcomes may additionally influence variation in interaction styles between caregivers and infants (Schmidt et al., 2023). Historically, the various Nigerian cultures have significantly shaped child-rearing practices. According to Akinware and Oguntuashe (2023), child-rearing pre-independence, was perceived as a collective duty rather than an individual responsibility. The traditional childrearing practices is within the extended family system or lineage, and the costs of raising children are not borne solely by the biological parents. Very close relatives also share the costs of rearing children, in terms of emotion, time, finance, and other material support, since all children together comprise the strength of the lineage (Ajayi & Owumi, 2013). It is in the confines of such communal childrearing practice that cultural values are nurtured, incubated, transferred into the next generation and retained. However, in many urbanized settings, the collectivist nature of childrearing seems to be diminishing for several reasons. A major case is the traditional role of grandparents as guardians of cultural heritage in the area of caregiving to very young children, which faces greater challenges due to factors like geographical separation or the demands of modern lifestyles (Makiwane & Kaunda, 2018).

In working paper 6 of the Core care conditions for children and families (Moore, 2024), emphasis was made on the importance of understanding diverse cultural norms in childcare practices. The paper highlighted that traditional Western models of child-rearing, which often focus on nuclear families, may not be universally applicable. Instead, anthropological evidence suggests that shared parenting, or alloparenting, is common in many cultures, where children are cared for by multiple caregivers. This diversity in caregiving practices can influence attachment styles and developmental outcomes, indicating that cultural context plays a crucial role in shaping child-rearing practices and expectations

2.1.2. Cultural and Responsive Childcare Practices and Child Reactive/Development Outcomes

Previous studies have drawn direct connections between responsive childrearing and child development outcomes (Scherer et al., 2019). Effects of responsive childcare practices on child development

outcomes have been uncovered over longitudinal and short-term studies. For the purpose of this study, we shall be considering short-term effects of responsive caregiving practices on interactions, reactions and development. The study by Frenkel, Bowman, Rousseau, and Mon (2024) explored how a mother's responsiveness to her baby's gaze at 4 months affects the baby's brain development and emotional behavior by 11 months. The findings suggest that mothers who respond to their baby's gaze in a timely and sensitive way can reduce the impact of early negative reactivity on brain activity, which in turn lowers the risk of emotional withdrawal and helps foster empathy in their infants. This highlights the importance of responsive caregiving in protecting against negative developmental outcomes. Another study found that responsive caregiving plays a key role in promoting positive socioemotional behaviours for children in rural Pakistan. This association remained significant even after accounting for factors like economic status and maternal depression, suggesting that improved caregiving practices can enhance child development in low-resource settings (Scherer et al., 2019).

Studies have also shown increasing paternal engagement in stimulation is likely to improve early child development in LMICs (Jeong, McCoy, Yousafzai, Salhi, & Fink, 2016). However, there is a clear separation of childrearing tasks between mothers and fathers—caregiving versus material provision—related to cultural gendered divisions of household roles and labour. Mothers' sociocultural duties as wives physically tie them to the house and childrearing; fathers' income-generating activities, however, often kept them away from the house, limiting their time and ability to perform direct childcare tasks (Hollowell et al., 2019). Nigeria being a patriarchal society, men enjoy hegemony over decision-making on important issues, like the care of children but are rarely involved in the child-rearing process, where in many cases young men sometimes get married and keep their wives and children back at home while they maintain a separate home in the city where they work, thereby leaving little or no room for responsive interaction between the men and their infants and toddlers (Ajayi & Owumi, 2013). This may however not be the same situation for nucleated families living together in urban low-income communities.

Responsiveness in caregiving practices can also be seen as a shared responsibility between adult and sibling/children caregivers of infants and toddlers in cultural communal settings where adult caregivers focus on the young child's physical needs and aim to keep them in a calm emotional state, while other young related children are the most crucial partners when it comes to play, face-to-face interaction, and the exchange of intense emotions (Scheidecker, 2023). It is also common to see caregiver activities

with young children as predominantly instructive, where the caregiver initiates interactions, with limited responsive interaction and stimulation (Hollowell et al., 2019). The study by Lavelli et al. (2019), on emotional co-regulation highlights Cameroonian Nso mothers' unique proximal co-regulation practices with infants aged 2-3 months. Nso mothers use body contact and rhythmical synchronization to regulate emotions, emphasizing maternal responsiveness in structuring and monitoring their infants. This approach fosters emotional co-regulation through bodily warmth and interaction, rather than facial expressiveness more common among western cultures. The asymmetrical interaction, where mothers lead and infants adjust, promotes early self-regulation which complies with cultural values. These findings reveal how cultural practices shape developmental pathways, offering insights into the integration of traditional and hybrid caregiving strategies in different cultural contexts.

Unfortunately, there are some down-sides as to how cultural beliefs, practices and expectations influence responsiveness in caregivers. A qualitative study exploring norms, beliefs, and practices of caregivers of young children in rural Burkina Faso was conducted by Dumbaugh et al., (Dumbaugh et al., 2023) and results revealed that talking and playing with babies and younger children were perceived to have little developmental impact. Caregivers felt their role in helping their children achieve later in life was to pay for education, save money, provide advice and be good role models. Interaction and learning activities were not specifically mentioned. Cultural values that prioritize obedience to elders and conformity influence how caregivers approach discipline and guidance. In Nigeria, children experience harsh treatment in form of discipline from their caregivers including their parents. Under normal circumstances, the cry of a baby should attract attention, love and care; instead it attracts aggressive responses from caregivers at home, in day-care centers and in schools (Ajayi & Owumi, 2013). According to the Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) of 2021, the percentage of children (aged 24-59 months) with whom any adult household member had engaged in 4 or more activities to provide early stimulation and responsive care in the last 3 days was 54.8% in Nigeria. Unfortunately, similar data have never been collected on a nationwide survey for children younger than 24 months.

2.1.3 The Mediating Role of Economic Factors

Conditions under which families raise children, shaped by their cultural backgrounds, affect their ability to provide nurturing care and stimulating environments (Moore, 2024) in a responsive way. To

fully understand childcare practices and the influence of cultural determinants on the responsivity of the caregiver, we need to be aware of socio-economic gradients. Family economic status is a powerful influencer in the interactions between cultural norms and caregiving practices.

A family's economic status is typically a combined measure of total family income, parent education, and parent occupation (Mao, 2022; Osei-Owusu, Ampofo, Akyina, Ampomah, & Osei-Owusu, 2018; Stevens & Featherman, 1981). Families living in different economic conditions experience varying levels of access to resources, which directly impacts their ability to provide nurturing environments for their children (Moore, 2024). Therefore, economic disparities can lead to significant differences in child outcomes.

The report in June 2023 by the International Finance Corporation highlights key statistics on women's economic contributions in Nigeria. In 2021, only 52% of women participated in the workforce, compared to 64% of men, reflecting a significant gender gap. Additionally, only 6% of women are employed in the formal wage sector, with many underemployed due to childcare responsibilities. The World Bank estimates that closing this gender gap in key sectors could boost Nigeria's economy by \$23 billion, or 6% of its GDP. The COVID-19 pandemic further emphasized the crucial role of childcare, as many women left the workforce due to insufficient childcare, negatively impacting GDP (Casanova et al., 2023).

Lagos State grapples with profound economic challenges that significantly impact women and child-rearing, particularly for infants and toddlers. Rapid population growth, with an average annual rate of 3.2%, has led to a housing deficit of approximately 3.3 million units, forcing many families into informal settlements where living conditions are substandard. This overcrowding exacerbates the lack of access to essential services, with only 14% of households receiving reliable electricity and just 35% having access to clean water (World Bank Group & Sustainable Urban and Regional Development, 2023).

Childcare in Nigeria is noted to be costly, with an average annual expense of about ₦228,000 for one child, which constitutes 63 percent of the annual minimum wage. Many families reported spending between 10 percent and 20 percent of their income on childcare services, which places a significant financial strain on them (Casanova et al., 2023). Women, often the primary caregivers, face heightened difficulties in managing household responsibilities under these conditions. Couples in polygynous

homes typically maintain separate purses and consequently share childrearing costs disproportionately, women often being made to bear more of the cost of raising and caring for children (Ajayi & Owumi, 2013). Limited access to healthcare services compromises maternal and child health, with inadequate sanitation facilities posing risks to infants and toddlers. High unemployment rates and the prevalence of informal employment further restrict women's economic opportunities, making it challenging to provide for their families. Moreover, the stress of navigating these economic barriers can adversely affect parenting practices, leading to negative outcomes for child development. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering a supportive environment for women and ensuring the well-being of infants and toddlers in Lagos State.

2.1.4. The Moderating Roles of Support Networks and Paid Childcare Services

All parents and caregivers need strong social support networks, people who they can rely on to support them in emotional and practical ways (Moore, 2024). In the Nigerian culture, right from birth, surrogate mothers, maybe either mother-in-laws or sister-in-laws from either the husband's or wife's family, make themselves available to assist in caring for the newborn baby and the nursing mother (Ajayi & Owumi, 2013). Responsiveness in caregiving practices can also be seen as a shared responsibility between adult and sibling/children caregivers (Scheidecker, 2023). According to the Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) of 2021, the percentage of children under age 5 left alone or under the supervision of another child younger than 10 years of age for more than 1 hour at least once in the last week was 43.5% in Nigeria. Caregivers who live in particularly stressful contexts, like many communities in low and middle income countries (LMICs) are likely to need additional support to be able to engage in optimal caregiving (Gilmour, 2018)

Major issues necessitating the need for involvement of grandparents and other forms of support networks is that a growing number of women are working. In Pakistan, a significant number of grandmothers take care of their grandchildren while their parents work or study and in recent years, this role has increased multifold because of the increased presence of women in workforce and women getting into higher education post children (Rahat, Sadaf, & Yunus, 2023). In China, urbanization has created up to 60 million 'left behind' Chinese children, or about one fifth of all Chinese children, who are growing up in the Chinese countryside while their parents live and work away, manning the factories and shops which are bringing about China's economic miracle. In Romania, it is estimated

that 350,000 children are 'left behind' while their parents are working abroad. Similarly, in the Philippines, large numbers of children are living with grandparents or relatives while their parents work abroad (Buchanan & Rotkirch, 2018).

However, the moderating effects of support networks experience alterations in their dynamics in low-income communities in urban states. A 2023 empirical study conducted by the Doha International Family Institute (DIFI) across 19 Arab countries, pointed out that urbanization can disrupt traditional support systems for child-rearing. As families move to urban areas, the geographical distance between extended family members often increases, which limits the support that couples receive. This reduction in proximity may place additional pressure on marital relationships, as couples may have to navigate parenting challenges without the extensive family support typically available in rural settings (Aref et al., 2024). Also, according to the Lagos state household survey report (2021), Lagos West, where Alimosho LGA is located, the report showed childcare to be the highest need households had to rely on neighbors for (16%). The results of this study imply a tendency for cultural norms that influence caregiving practices to be watered down in the absence of familiar support as well as the reduction of responsiveness during caregiving in parents where decreased proximity to support increases stress.

Nurturing environments, characterized by care, positive interactions, and individualized attention, are crucial for fostering positive developmental outcomes in children. Early learning programs, including formal and community-based preschools in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), significantly improve children's cognitive and psychosocial development, although their impact on physical growth and motor skills is less clear. The effectiveness of these programs depends on their quality, with key factors being the availability of diverse play materials, interactive reading, classroom organization, and instructional support (Britto et al., 2017). In rapidly urbanizing areas of sub-Saharan Africa, paid, informal childcare is becoming the norm for many preschool children. This growing trend, especially in low-income urban communities, is driven by changing patterns of work, social structures, and gender norms, more mothers joining the workforce and working long hours, the rise of highly nucleated families, and the welcomed increase in school enrollment for older siblings. However, few studies that exist suggest that the quality is often poor, posing risks to the early development of these vulnerable children (Clark et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2021; Oloo et al., 2023). ECCE programs, in low-income communities, are described to suffer from poor quality due to inadequate resources, infrastructure, and training for educators resulting in limited impact on child development and school

readiness(Maleq, Fuentes, & Akkari, 2022). According to a news article by Business Day (Ogwo, 2024), the number of uneducated ECDE teachers in Nigeria is a large 24.7 percent of the total and over 50 percent have OND which may be unrelated to ECCE. However, there is currently little or no support in many sub-saharan countries to ensure these services provide safe, nurturing care accessible to low-income families(Oloo et al., 2023). The lack of reliable and affordable childcare options has a considerable impact on the productivity of working parents. The Investing In Childcare report(Casanova et al., 2023) found that over half (57 percent) of women and one third (33 percent) of men reported that the absence of quality childcare affected their productivity at work, leaving us with the question of how these factors may influence responsive childcare practices.

Another aspect to consider is how cultural childcare practices are altered as a result of the moderating effect of these paid childcare services. According to Nwoke (2013), who conducted a purely qualitative research reviewing relevant studies investigating the influence of cultural value systems and the home on child-rearing practices, findings buttressed studies that highlighted how modernity has affected child-rearing practices. Work-family role conflict in modern society has a negative influence on the child-rearing value system. Children are left under the care of a mother surrogate type in the day-care or with in-home nannies from a critical tender age, people who may be foreign to their cultural value systems, thereby strange values may be transmitted to the children through interaction with the caregiver and most of the home values which the child should have internalized in the home become strange or foreign to the child. Although Nwoke's study widely captured input from a variety of cultural groups in Nigeria, a significant gap in this study lies in the age of respondents in the semi-structured interview which were of an average age of 65 years. The study did not capture the impute of parents actively transferring values while rearing young children at the time of the study. A quantitative survey would have also strengthened findings.

2.1.5. Development Outcomes of Children in the Early Years

Culturally responsive childcare practices can significantly impact child development outcomes (Moore, 2024). The early years are a fertile ground for blossoming minds and thriving bodies. Yet, in the kaleidoscope of low-income urban communities, the intricate tapestry of cultural caregiving practices intertwines with economic realities, potentially influencing children's cognitive, social, emotional, and

physical trajectories. This point delves into the fertile soil of child development outcomes, exploring how culturally-influenced caregiving practices might shape the saplings of young lives.

Cultural practices around communication, touch, and discipline can nurture or impede cognitive development. In rural Burkina Faso, for instance, Dumbaugh et al., (2023) found that mothers' deemphasis on talking with their infants may inhibit language development and secure attachment, while the study by Lavelli et.al (2019), on emotional co-regulation highlights Cameroonian Nso mothers' unique proximal co-regulation practices with infants aged 2-3 months. However, cultural norms around punishment can have detrimental effects. Nsamenang (2008) in Cameroon highlighted the potential for physical punishment to impair cognitive and social development, emphasizing the need for culturally sensitive interventions that promote positive discipline practices.

Social and emotional development also flourish within the embrace of cultural caregiving (Yang & Wang, 2019). Different cultures exhibit distinct yet beneficial caregiver-child interaction styles. For instance, urban middle-class families in Costa Rica engage in dyadic play, reflecting a distal parenting style, while rural indigenous families emphasize care over play, showcasing a more proximal approach (Schmidt, Keller, & Rosabal Coto, 2023). However, cultural practices that emphasize stoicism or suppress emotional expression can impede emotional development (Ajayi & Owumi, 2013). Understanding these diverse cultural pathways is crucial for designing interventions that nurture healthy social and emotional growth.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

This study decided to utilize the Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological Theory Revision: Moving Culture From the Macro Into the Micro (Vélez-Agosto, Soto-Crespo, Vizcarrondo-Oppenheimer, Vega-Molina, & García Coll, 2017) as its primary theoretical framework as this revised version effectively captures the interplay between individual, family, community, and cultural factors in shaping child development and care and explicitly focuses on culture as an integral part of the microsystem, which aligns perfectly with the research objectives.

Instead of treating culture as a distinct macrosystem as in the past, the updated version of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory discussed in the review stresses the crucial role that culture plays in and across the levels of human development, contending that culture is a part of the microsystems that directly affect child development rather than being an outside force. Intimate settings like the home, daycare or school, and peer groupings are examples of microsystems. Development is heavily influenced by cultural practices and norms, which in turn shape interactions within these settings. Cultural norms and values define and structure the relationships and interactions within these systems, which is why culture is thought of as a central element of development

The concept of "operationalization" of culture in the bioecological theory, refers to the way that cultural norms and values define and structure the relationships and interactions that take place within microsystems. This viewpoint emphasizes how cultural contexts have an impact on daily routines, practices, and activities, which is important to know in order to comprehend developmental processes of infants and toddlers. The updated model also places a strong emphasis on proximal processes, or the interactions that occur between people and their immediate surroundings, as being essential to human development. Cultural factors have an impact on these processes, indicating that studying how cultural norms show up in day-to-day interactions and caregiving practices is necessary to understand child development.

The theory recognizes that different systems—micro, meso, and exosystems, among others—interact with one another. The theory also expands on how they affect development as a whole. The interaction of cultural factors with other contextual elements like economic status and community resources shapes individual experiences. Notable theorists who highlight the interdependence of culture and context, such as Vygotsky, Rogoff, and Weisner, have influenced the revised theory. This incorporation stimulates scholars to contemplate how cultural settings influence personal encounters and developmental paths.

2.3. Conceptual Framework

The study's conceptual framework reveals the interaction of all variables involved in the study. Variables include:

1. Independent Variable:

- Cultural norms: These are the shared beliefs, values, and behaviors that shape caregiving practices within Agbado Oke-odo, Ipaja-Ayobo, and Mosan-okunola LCDA's in Alimosho LGA. Cultural norms influence how caregivers interact with infants and toddlers in terms of communication, touch, discipline, learning, and emotional support.

2. Dependent Variables:

- Responsive caregiving practices: These are the behaviors and actions exhibited by caregivers towards infants and toddlers, in responding sensitively, warmly and timely to their needs.
- Child development outcomes: These encompass cognitive, social, emotional, and physical domains of development in infants and toddlers, which are influenced by the quality of caregiving practices and the cultural context in which they occur.

3. Mediating and/or Moderating Variables:

- economic factors: These variables, such as poverty, housing instability, and access to formal childcare, may mediate the relationship between cultural norms and caregiving practices. They

can influence how cultural norms manifest in caregiving behaviors within low-income urban communities.

- Social support networks and paid childcare services: These variables can moderate the relationship between cultural norms, economic realities, and responsive caregiving practices. Strong social support networks may enhance the positive impact of cultural norms on caregiving practices and paid childcare services may provide additional support and resources to caregivers in the selected low-income urban communities.

The Figure 2.1 below is a schematic representation of the conceptual framework

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Area

This research was conducted in selected Local Community Development Areas (LCDAs) of Alimosho Local Government Area (LGA) in Lagos, Nigeria.

Figure 3.1: Image of Lagos state, Alimosho LGA highlighted

Alimosho is the largest LGA in Lagos State, Nigeria, with a projected population of about 4,082,900 in 2019. Initially established in 1945 under the Western Region, it has since been subdivided into six Local Community Development Areas (LCDA): Agbado/Oke-odo, Ayobo/Ipaja, Alimosho, Egbe/Idimu, Ikotun/Igando, and Mosan Okunola. The population is predominantly Yoruba, especially

the Egba and Egbado subgroups, and major religions include Islam, Christianity, and Yoruba traditional beliefs, with Yoruba as the widely spoken language. Economically, Alimosho thrives on commerce, supported by major markets like Ikotun, Igando, and Akesan, as well as a variety of private and public institutions, including hotels and banks. It is known as the noisiest alongside the most populous LGA in Lagos State. Fifteen home and center-based daycare facilities within these communities were selected as study locations within three Local Council Development Areas (LCDAs) in Alimosho LGA- Agbado Oke-Odo, Ipaja-Ayobo, and Mosan Okunola LCDAs. These centers provided the environment for most of the research activities, including observations and interviews.

3.2 Materials and Equipment

The following tools and materials were used during the research:

1. **Survey questionnaire:** A structured tool designed for the purpose of this study and used to gather information on demography, economic status, cultural norms and caregiving decisions, and factors affecting caregiving practices. Tool was pretested and obtained a reliability coefficient of 0.706
2. **Caregiver-Reported Early Child Development Index (CREDI):** A standardized assessment used to evaluate cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development in infants and toddlers (Waldman et al., 2021). Cronbach's alpha coefficients calculated for this tool suggested acceptable internal consistency/inter-item reliability for motor ($\alpha = .68$), cognitive ($\alpha = .90$), and socioemotional ($\alpha = .68$) items (McCoy et al., 2017; Waldman et al., 2021), and has been validated for use via various studies even in African and low-income communities.
3. **Observation of Mother-Child Interaction (OMCI) tool:** An internationally validated tool used to measure parental sensitivity and responsiveness. OMCI shows high reliability with an alpha of 0.886 for total score, 0.829 for mother score and 0.780 for child score (Rasheed & Yousafzai, 2015; Scherer et al., 2019).
4. **Audio recorders:** For recording interviews and focus group discussions.
5. **Video recording equipment:** Used to capture live interactions between mothers and children during OMCI observations.
6. **Data analysis software:** SPSS (version 27) was used for quantitative data, and NVivo for qualitative data analysis.

3.3 Research Design

A mixed-methods approach was adopted to explore the relationship between cultural norms, economic contexts, and responsive childcare practices. The study combined both quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews and observations.

3.3.1 Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling was used to select participants, with selection based on having children within the ages of birth to 36 months and their accessibility. The snowballing technique was later used to obtain participants for focus group discussions, ensuring diverse representation.

3.3.2 Sample Size

The study worked with 15 childcare centers, each having an average of 10 children within the target age bracket. The quantitative survey targeted all parents associated with these centers, aiming for a broad representation of caregiving practices. In total, 75-100 mothers were purposively sampled for the survey, resulting in 89 valid responses being collected. For the Observation of Mother-Child Interaction (OMCI), a subset of 20 mothers was purposefully selected from the broader survey group. These participants were chosen to represent diverse caregiving styles for more in-depth observation of caregiver-child interactions.

For the qualitative interviews, 8 mothers were purposively selected to provide a deeper understanding of cultural caregiving practices and their impact on caregiving practices. Finally, focus group discussions involved between 5-15 participants per group, with a total of 7 groups representing different community segments. These groups included a mix of mothers, grand mothers, aunts, paid caregivers, and other community stakeholders to explore broader cultural and economic influences on caregiving. 29 responses were also collected from paid childcare providers across the centers, offering insights into formal caregiving practices.

3.4 Data Collection

3.4.1 Quantitative Data Collection

The primary data collection tool for the quantitative aspect was a structured questionnaire administered to mothers and primary caregivers in the selected daycare facilities. The Caregiver-Reported Early Child Development Index (CREDI) was also administered to assess the cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development of infants and toddlers. A total of 89 responses were obtained from mothers.

3.4.2 Qualitative Data Collection

- 1. In-depth Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 8 mothers to gain deeper insights into their caregiving practices, cultural norms, and perceptions of child development.
- 2. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs):** Seven focus group discussions were conducted with mothers, caregivers (grandparents and aunties), community stakeholders (including one traditional leader, 2 religious leaders), and paid childcare providers, to explore broader perspectives on child-rearing, cultural influences, and caregiving challenges. These FGDs were held at various locations, including childcare centers, homes, elder care centers, churches, and in community leaders' compounds.
- 3. OMCI Observations:** The OMCI tool was used to observe 20 mothers from the survey sample. Live video recordings were taken of a 5-minute interaction between mothers and their children, either reading a book together (for children between the ages of 1-2.5years) or solving a Duplo blocks challenge (for children between the ages of 2.5 and 3.5 years), depending on the child's age. Interactions were scored immediately after the first video replay

3.5 Data Analysis

3.5.1 Quantitative Data

The quantitative data collected from surveys were entered into a statistical software package SPSS (version 27) and cleaned for missing values, outliers, and inconsistencies. Descriptive statistics were

used to summarize key variables, and bivariate and multivariate analyses were conducted to test hypotheses related to cultural norms, economic context, caregiving practices, and child reactions and development outcomes.

3.5.2 Qualitative Data

The qualitative data from interviews and FGDs were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. Thematic analysis was performed using NVivo software to code and categorize recurring themes such as cultural norms, economic context, and responsive caregiving. Both inductive and deductive approaches were used to explore emergent themes and draw meaningful insights beyond the predefined research questions.

3.5.3 Mixed-Methods Integration

Findings from both the quantitative and qualitative data were triangulated to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. The integration of data from multiple sources helped validate the results and ensure a holistic analysis of caregiving practices in the context of cultural and economic factors.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from formal childcare centers where participants were recruited. Informed consent was secured from all participants before data collection began. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the research, and culturally sensitive practices were adopted to ensure respect for local customs. Participants were clearly informed of the potential benefits and risks of the study, and the results were shared with the communities involved.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results

4.1.1. Demographic Data of Respondents

The demographic data of the respondents are shown in Table 4.1. below. From the Table 4.1., majority (95.5%) of the respondents were female, with only 4.5% being male. Almost half of the respondents (48.3%) were between the ages of 25-34 years and 35-44 years, with smaller groups in other age brackets. A significant portion (57.3%) of the respondents had attained higher education, while 15.7% had completed OND/Diploma, and 4.5% had only primary school education. The majority (96.6%) were married, and majority of respondents (79.8%) identified as Yoruba. Most respondents (78.7%) lived in nucleated households with 2-5 people. Regarding children in the household, 44.9% had two children, 24.7% had one child, and 64% had at least one child under the age of 4. A little over half of the children engaged in the study were male (53.9%), while almost half (46.1%) were female. Regarding age, 26.9% of children were between the ages of 1-10 months, 29.2% between 11- 20 months, while some (32.6%) were within the 21-30 months age range and the least amount falling between 31-40 months (11.2%).

Table 4.1: Demographic Factor of Parent Respondents (N=89)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	4	4.5
Female	85	95.5
Age (years)		
18 – 24	1	1.1
25 – 34	43	48.3
35 – 44	43	48.3
45 – 54	2	2.2
Highest Level of Education		
Primary school	4	4.5
Secondary school	16	18
Vocational training	4	4.5
OND/Diploma	14	15.7
Higher education	51	57.3
Marital Status		
Married	86	96.6
Single	1	1.1
Divorced/separated	2	2.2
Cultural Background		
Yoruba	71	79.8
Igbo	9	10.1
Others	9	10.1
People living in your household		
1-5	70	78.7
6-10	16	18
11-15	3	3.4
No children you have currently living with you		
1	22	24.7
2	40	44.9
3	17	19.1
More than 3	10	11.2
Number of children under age 4 living in the household		
None	8	9

1	57	64
2	19	21.3
3	5	5.6
Your relationship to these children		
I am their parent	85	95.5
I am their relative (grandparent, aunty, uncle, etc)	1	1.1
I am their guardian (not related but child lives with you)	1	1.1
Others	2	2.2
Support network (friends, family, neighbors) to assist with caregiving		
Yes, a strong support network	21	23.6
Yes, a moderate support network	14	15.7
Yes, but limited support	16	18
No support network	38	42.7
Variable	Frequency	Percentage

The demographic profile of the caregivers shows several important aspects of the childcare facilities and the staff managing them. Many (75%) of the facilities are center or school-based, while only 24.1% operate as home-based daycares. Regarding the roles within these facilities, some (58.6%) of the respondents are teachers, followed by directors (27.6%). In terms of experience, some (41.4%) of the respondents have over 6 years of childcare experience. however, more than half (55.2%) of the respondents had never received formal training. A little over half (51.6%) of caregivers indicate a child-to-caregiver ratio of 1:6-1:10.

Table 4.2 : Demographics Characteristics of Respondents(N=29)

Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Type of Childcare facility	Home-based daycare	7	24.1
	Center/school-based daycare	22	75
Position held	Director	8	27.6
	Teacher	17	58.6
	Caregiver	4	13.8
Years of experience in childcare	Less than 1 years	6	20.7
	1-3 years	8	27.6
	4-6years	3	10.3
	More than 6 years	12	41.4
Last time you received formal early childcare training	Never	16	55.2
	3 to 5 years	4	13.8
	1-2 years	6	20.7
	6 to 12 months ago	1	3.4
	Less than 6 months ago	2	6.9
Age group of children cared for	Infants (0-12 months)	2	6.9
	Toddlers (1-3 years)	10	34.5
	Preschool (3-5 years)	5	17.2
	6 to 12 years	2	6.9
	Infants (0-12 months), Toddlers (1-3 years)	6	20.7
	Infants (0-12 months), Toddlers (1-3 years), Preschool (3-5 years)	1	3.4
	Preschool (3-5 years), 6 to 12 years	1	3.4
	Infants (0-12 months), Toddlers (1-3 years), Preschool (3-5 years), 6 to 12 years	2	6.9
Typical child-to-caregiver ratio	1:1-1:5	4	13.8
	1:6-1:10	15	51.6
	1:11-1:15	2	6.8
	2:1-2:10	6	20.6
	2:10-2:20	2	6.8
The challenge of managing the daily number of children	Not challenging at all	5	17.2

	Somewhat challenging	4	13.8
	Challenging	13	44.8
	Very challenging	6	20.7
	Extremely challenging	1	3.4
Length of stay of children in the centre daily	4 to 6 hours	2	6.9
	7 to 9 hours	21	72.4
	10 to 12 hours	6	20.7
Challenge of managing the daily number of children for such hours	Not challenging at all	3	10.3
	Somewhat challenging	3	10.3
	Challenging	15	51.7
	Very challenging	7	24.1
	Extremely challenging	1	3.4
Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage

4.1.2. Cultural Norms and Responsive Caregiving Practices

Many respondents (48.3%) reported that cultural norms had a moderate to strong influence on their caregiving decisions. Family involvement remained crucial, with 47.2% of respondents stating that family involvement was very important in raising children. A large portion (58.4%) were in moderate to strong agreement that grandparents provided the best care for children, reflecting the cultural tradition of extended family involvement. The most frequently mentioned source of parenting guidance was the mother highlighting the trust and reliance placed on grandmother/maternal wisdom.

Table 4.3a: Cultural norms and caregiving of respondents (N=89)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Extent to which cultural norms influence your decisions regarding caregiving practices		
Strongly agree	10	11.2
Agree	33	37.1
Disagree	29	32.6
Strongly disagree	17	19.1
The person in the family that typically helps you care for your children when needed		
Spouse/Partner	56	62.9
Grandparents	12	13.5
Older child	10	11.2
Other relatives	3	3.4
No one	8	9
Living together with any extended family members (grandparents, aunts, uncles)		
Yes	23	25.8
No	66	74.2
Family involvement is important in raising children		
Strongly Agree	42	47.2
Neutral	26	29.2
Strongly Disagree	21	23.6
Cultural norms in community assign child caregiving roles based on gender		
Strongly Agree	18	20.2
Strongly Disagree	47	52.8
Neutral	24	27
Grandparents give better care to children than any other family members		
Strongly agree	27	30.3
Moderately Agree	25	28.1
Disagree	24	27
Strongly Disagree	13	14.6
Who usually takes care of the very young children (0-3) in the family		

Mother only	10	11.2
Father only	1	1.1
Both parents equally	44	49.4
Both parents but NOT equally	34	38.2

The person that usually make decisions about childcare in your family

Mother only	5	5.6
Father only	3	3.4
Both parents together	81	91

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
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Table 4.3b: Cultural Norms and Caregiving of Respondents (N=89)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Religion or cultural beliefs influence caregiving decisions		
Strongly Agree	26	29.2
Strongly Disagree	56	62.9
Neutral	7	7.9
It is important to maintain cultural traditions in caregiving practices		
Strongly Agree	42	47.2
Strongly Disagree	47	52.8
Family traditions or how people around raise children affect how you want to raise your own children		
Strongly Agree	21	23.6
Strongly Disagree	64	71.9
Neutral	4	4.5
Feel comfortable speaking openly about caregiving needs within your family		
Strongly Agree	39	43.8
Agree	41	46.1
Strongly Disagree	9	10.1
Cultural norms influence your choice of childcare arrangements		
Strongly Agree	23	25.8
Neutral	37	41.6
Strongly Disagree	29	32.6
Cultural beliefs ever influenced your decision to use daycare services		
Strongly Agree	14	15.7
Strongly Disagree	70	78.7
Neutral	5	5.6
Think cultural norms prioritize certain caregiving practices over others		
Strongly Agree	17	19.1
Strongly Disagree	44	49.4
Neutral	28	31.5
Feel cultural norms support your caregiving responsibilities		
Strongly Agree	23	25.8
Strongly Disagree	7	7.9
Disagree	40	44.9
Neutral	19	21.3
Variables	Frequency	Percentage

During qualitative interviews, The respondents revealed a variety of traditional caregiving methods, which are deeply rooted in cultural beliefs. A common practice is the use of warm water for bathing and the application of palm oil on the baby's skin, which is believed to prevent body odour and maintain the baby's skin health. Massaging the baby's body, particularly the navel, legs, and hands, was also frequently mentioned, as it is thought to promote relaxation, proper development, and aid sleep. Some respondents mentioned additional practices, such as throwing the baby up to reduce their fear of heights and massaging with a hot towel or hot lantern for navel care. These practices are aimed at strengthening the baby physically and preparing them for future challenges.

As mentioned by some of the respondents

"We rub the baby with palm oil to avoid body odor and massage the navel with a hot towel and clean it after." (28 years, Primary)

"We throw the baby up so they won't be scared of height." (30 years, Vocational training)

"We massage the baby's body, legs, and hands because it helps them sleep well." (39 years, OND)

Respondents however did express discomfort with certain childcare practices prevalent in their culture. A notable concern was the practice of vigorous shaking or tossing of babies. Additionally, the use of hot water for massages was mentioned and criticized. Similarly, a third respondent voiced a preference for gentler methods. These responses indicate a growing awareness and questioning of traditional practices, emphasising a desire for safer and more comfortable alternatives. According to some of the respondents:

"I don't feel comfortable with shaking the baby rigorously and throwing them upside down." (31 years, Secondary school)

"I don't appreciate using hot water for massage; I prefer oil." (30 years, Secondary school)

In families with young children (0-3 years), almost half (49.4%) of respondents reported that caregiving responsibilities were shared equally between both parents, however cultural perceptions

played a significant role as respondent generally concurred on the belief that culturally women are expected to be responsible for child rearing tasks. According to one respondent:

"Nigerian men have pride and might think of what people will say." (56 years, Female HND/Degree)

Responsive caregiving was opined to be culturally associated with pampering children. The analysis of responses revealed a spectrum of opinions regarding the concept of pampering a child. Most participants associated pampering with spoiling, suggesting that it could lead to negative behavior if not managed properly. The respondents generally defined "pampering a child" as behavior that involved excessive leniency, cuddling, or avoiding necessary correction due to the perception that the child was too young to understand their actions. Several respondents believed that pampering occurred when a parent or caregiver indulged a child's demands or avoided discipline, even when the child misbehaved or took something that was not theirs. According to some of the respondents:

"Pampering is when you are supposed to correct a child and you do not because you feel they are too young to understand." (36 years, HND/Degree)

"When children take what is not theirs or cry for what is not theirs and you give it to them, I don't like pampering my child." (38 years, HND)

However, there was a nuanced view among some respondents who felt that a certain level of pampering was natural and acceptable, as even adults enjoy being pampered. The consensus appeared to be that while occasional pampering was not inherently harmful, overindulgence might foster undesirable behavior patterns in children. According to the respondents:

"Pampering is spoiling the child, and culturally, it's giving negative behavior." (36 years, Secondary school)

"People feel when you pamper a child, you are spoiling the child, meanwhile even we as adults want to be pampered; I don't think there's any problem with pampering, but over-pampering might be bad." (34 years, HND)

Opinions also varied regarding whether children aged 0-36 months can be overly pampered, with some respondents asserting that they can be, while others believe that it was impossible at this age, indicating a need for nurturing rather than concern for over pampering.

Respondents highlighted the common practice of co-sleeping among parents, primarily for reasons of comfort and convenience. Several respondents mentioned that they preferred co-sleeping because their babies were more comfortable and slept better when sharing a bed with them. Co-sleeping was also seen as beneficial for closely monitoring the baby, especially for breastfeeding mothers who found it easier to attend to their babies during the night. The age at which children are expected to move out of their parents' bed varied. Many respondents suggested that this transition typically happened around the age of two when the child could either sleep with older siblings or independently. However, the decision also depended on the available space in the home and individual upbringing. Some of the respondents said-

"Yes, because I read about co-sleeping, and I monitor my baby; she likes to sleep in the same space as me, and that's better for me because of breastfeeding." (36 years, HND Female)

"It depends on the space I have in my house, and the way you are brought up also matters." (38 years, OND Female)

In exploring specific responsive caregiving behaviours, during Focus Group Discussions and In-Depth-Interviews, the study categorised discussions of maternal responsive behaviours into four components: (1) contingent responding, (2) emotional-affective support, (3) support for infant foci of attention and (4) language inputs, in line with the conceptual model for the OMCI tool, (based on a theoretical framework reported by Landry, Smith, & Swank (2006).

Respondents shared various strategies to soothe a non-stop fussy baby, highlighting a mix of practical and emotional responsive approach. Common techniques included feeding practices, bathing the baby, and using physical comfort methods like carrying or "backing" (a traditional practice of carrying a baby on the back). Some respondents emphasized the importance of checking the baby for injuries or using trial-and-error to determine what the child needed. Emotional support methods, such as singing or cuddling, also emerged as popular strategies. Interestingly, some respondents mentioned spanking, illustrating parenting philosophies associating fussiness from infants and toddlers as misbehaving.

Overall, the responses reflected a blend of nurturing and problem-solving techniques aimed at promptly calming a distressed child. As stated by some of the respondents:

"I will give her medicine when she cries excessively." (30 years, Secondary school)

"I will bath the baby if she crying and refusing to settle." (56 years, HND/Degree)

When discussing reactions to a child tripping or falling, mothers responded that they maintained calmness, looked away or did not respond abruptly in order not to trigger crying. Respondents exhibited a range of strategies for responding to unwanted behaviors in their children, with a notable emphasis on physical discipline. Many participants indicated that spanking or beating was their primary method of correction, reflecting a more traditional approach to discipline as there was a consensus on the belief that toddlers and even infants are fully aware of their misbehaviours and needed to be corrected promptly and sternly for effective discipline. However, some respondents also highlighted the importance of verbal correction and communication. According to the respondents,

"... for my son, he knows oh! He will just bite my breast and look to see how I will react. Then I will just frown my face or I will smack him" (30 years, Secondary school)

"Give him small bite on his forehead! He will never try it again." (62 years, HND/Degree in response)

Respondents identified key signs to determine when a baby is full after eating or ready for sleep. A consistent indicator mentioned was the baby's behavior, particularly stopping to suck or eat. These responses reflect a shared understanding and sensitivity to baby's cues such as cessation of feeding, are crucial for recognizing their needs, highlighting the importance of attentive observation in caregiving. As mentioned by some of the respondents:

"He will stop sucking." (56 years, HND/Degree)

"He will stop eating." (31 years, Secondary school)

The data revealed that caregivers adopted a diverse range of language inputs while interacting with their babies and toddlers. Most caregivers used calm and gentle tones, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a soothing environment. They also engaged in playful communication, often using baby

talk during playtime, while some switched to a more serious tone when correcting the child. Affectionate nicknames were commonly used, with terms such as “Ayomide bobo” and “Juju” being examples. Singing was another widespread practice, with caregivers frequently mentioning songs like “Baby Shark” and “Ori mi ejika” to engage or calm their children. While singing was prevalent, storytelling and reading appeared less common, with only a few participants engaging in this activity. Additionally, when comforting a crying child, caregivers often used familiar songs or repetitive phrases alongside physical comfort, like holding or petting the child to create a soothing effect. Respondents mentioned this:

“Yes, when he is crying, I carry him and pet him, then sing his favorite songs, ‘Baby Shark’ and ‘Mummy mummy yes papa.’” (35 years, OND)

“I speak to her like a baby sometimes, and when correcting, I raise my voice.” (32 years, HND/Degree)

Touch played a significant role in how caregivers expressed affection to their babies and toddlers. Most caregivers frequently held and cuddled their children, with some mentioning that they did so particularly when the child was crying or upset. Physical closeness, such as carrying or backing children, was also common, as many caregivers believed it provided comfort and security. Affection was not limited to physical touch; caregivers also spoke about showing love through verbal expressions especially singing, and giving gifts like snacks, toys, and new clothes. Additionally, while some caregivers mentioned that there were situations when it was not appropriate to touch a child such as when disciplining the child, others felt that there was never a wrong time to touch their children. Some of the respondents said-

“I cuddle her a lot of times, and then she sings and pecks me too.” (32 years, HND/Degree)

“Yes, I back her because I believe she's more comfortable.” (40 years, HND/Degree)

There was a strong belief among caregivers that displaying happiness in front of children was essential, as children are perceptive to emotions and can pick up on their parents' feelings. Many caregivers emphasized the importance of discussing emotions, although some felt that infants and toddlers might not fully understand these concepts yet. According to a respondent,

“Yes, because children read emotions and they pick things; they pick words and reactions from their parents.” (38 years, HND)

During direct observation, language inputs and support for infant foci of attention were identified. The majority of mothers (80.0%) never expressed negative verbal statements, such as verbal scolding or using aggressive language. About half (50.0%) were sensitive to the child's needs, often following the child's lead and allowing them to explore freely. Also, some caregivers (35.0%) often pointed to and named objects in books and during activities and fewer mothers (15.0%) helped maintain the child's interest by actively engaging with the pictures and commenting on the child's actions. Unfortunately, many (60.0%) were never able to answer the child's questions or requests, providing little to no language stimulation and some caregivers (40.0%) never expressed positive verbal statements, praising the child or conveying love. See Table 4.4a below.

4.1.3. Effect of Culturally Influenced Caregiving on Child Interaction, Reactions, Responses, and Development

To draw inference, the study measured relationship between caregiver-child interaction behaviors and child engagement and emotional responses during caregiver interaction using direct observation scoring with the OMCI tool. The results are shown in Table 4.4 a, b and c below:

Table 4.4a: Caregiver to Child Interaction Behaviors

Variables	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
Shows positive affect for the child For example: Smiles at child, laughs with child, Speaks in a soft tone to the child	4 (20.0)	6(30.0)	7(35.0)	3(15.0)
Shows negative affect for the child For example: Show frustration with child, frowns at child, Disengaged from child for more than 10 seconds	5(25.0)	6(30.0)	9(45.0)	0(0.0)
Shows positive touch. For example: Strokes the child gently or touches the child with affection or kisses the child	11(55.0)	3(15.0)	4(20.0)	2(10.0)

Shows negative touch For example: Pushes child away, roughly handles child	9(45.0)	10(50.0)	0(0.0)	1(5.0)
Expresses positive verbal statements. For example: Praises the child for something related to picture, Praises the child for something else, Expresses love or affection verbally	8(40.0)	5(25.0)	3(15.0)	4(20.0)
Expresses negative verbal statements For example: Scolds child, aggressive or abusive language	16(80.0)	3(15.0)	1(5.0)	0(0.0)
Is sensitive of the child's needs. For example: Follows child's lead, Accepts child's disinteresting book and does not force infant to play with it any longer, Guides child in activity but allows the freedom to independently manipulate items, Allows child to explore book through developmentally appropriate means (mouthing or throwing)	10(50.0)	3(15.0)	5(25.0)	2(10.0)
Acceptance and responding Points and names object in book	5(25.0)	4(20.0)	4(20.0)	7(35.0)
Questions child. For example: Asks child to name an object in the picture, Asks child to point to an object, Asks question about meaning or interpretation of the picture Holds book for child to see Points to picture and says name of object Asks child "why" Asks child to interpret something in the picture (why something is happening)	10(50.0)	1(5.0)	5(25.0)	4(20.0)
Answers child's question or request. Language Stimulation Helps child to maintain interest.	12(60.0)	3(15.0)	2(10.0)	3(15.0)
For example: Tries to create interest in the pictures through verbalizing Helps the child explore the book Actively comments on the infant's actions	6(30.0)	6(30.0)	3(15.0)	5(25.0)

Variables	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
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Table 4.4b: Child Engagement and Emotional Responses During Caregiver Interaction

Variables	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
Smiles, laughs at caregiver	4(20.0)	8(40.0)	3(15.0)	5(25.0)
Shows excitement and enjoyment like clapping	8(40.0)	6(35.0)	4(20.0)	2(10.0)
Crying, frowning, frustrated	10(20.0)	4(40.0)	6(30.0)	0(0.0)
Explores the book for a significant time (for at least 1 minute). For example: Looks at pictures. Tries to turn page. Points to picture. Verbalizes to picture	0(0.0)	7(35.0)	7(35.0)	6(30.0)
Continues in spite of distractions	2(10.0)	9(45.0)	3(15.0)	6(30.0)
Vocalizing or producing words (12 m) uses words, joins word, comments on a picture or asks questions (24 m)	7(35.0)	4(20.0)	2(10.0)	7(35.0)
Expressing enjoyment while exploring together	4(20.0)	8(40.0)	5(25.0)	3(15.0)

Table 4.4c: Relationship between caregiver-child interaction behaviors and child engagement and emotional responses during caregiver interaction

	Mean	Correlation (r)	p-value
Caregiver-child interaction behaviors	17.2	0.692	<0.001*
Child engagement and emotional responses	11.1		

Pearson correlation showed a significant association between caregiver-child interaction behaviors and child engagement and emotional responses during caregiver interaction with p-value <0.001. The analysis showed a positive correlation (r=0.692) which increase in caregiver-child interaction behaviors lead to increase child engagement and emotional responses.

4.1.4. Economic Factors Mediating Cultural Norms and Caregiving

Most of the respondents (92.1%) reported having jobs that provided them with income. Among those who worked, 64% had jobs that required them to leave their homes, while 24.7% worked from home. Looking at employment status, 41.6% identified as self-employed, and 39.3% identified as full-time employees. When asked about their primary sources of income, 46.1% relied on money from jobs, and 44.9% indicated their own business. In terms of household income, 44.9% respondents earned N10,000-50,000 (\$6-\$30) monthly. Most respondents (94.4%) rented their homes, and over the past year and 37.1% reported moving homes more than once or faced difficulties paying rent.

Table 4.5a: Economic factor of respondents (N=89)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Currently have work that earns money		
Yes	82	92.1
No	7	7.9
Work outside home		
Yes, I have to leave my home to my workplace	57	64
No, I work from home	22	24.7
Sometimes I am able to work from home	6	6.7
Not applicable	4	4.5
Hours of working outside the home per day (including transportation time to and from work) (n=63)		
1-5	8	12.7
6-10	42	66.7
11-15	12	19
16-24	1	1.6
Employment status		
Employed full-time	35	39.3
Employed part-time	11	12.4
Self-employed	38	42.7

Homemaker	4	4.5
Other	1	1.1

Main income that is relied on

Money from a job or work	41	46.1
Money from your own business or work that you do yourself	40	44.9
Money from a pension or retirement plan	1	1.1
You own things that make you money(investments)	2	2.2
Support from family or friends	3	3.4
Remittances from family members abroad	1	1.1

Monthly household income range

10,000 -50,000 naira	40	44.9
60,000 – 100,000 naira	26	29.2
100,000 naira or more	23	25.8

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
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Financial management presented varying levels of difficulty as 31.5% had enough money to cover most of their expenses but struggle with some, 25.8% did not have enough money to cover all their expenses and often borrowed or use credit and 9% heavily relied on external help to manage household expenses. When it came to work interfering with caregiving, 36% said this happened occasionally and 22.5% said everytime. Regarding childcare, 65.2% used paid childcare service many, 18% mostly depended on unpaid childcare support from various social networks and 29.2% managed childcare responsibilities themselves most times to save cost. Unfortunately, financial challenges in the past year had impacted a little over half (51.7%) of the respondents’ ability to provide childcare. Finding childcare that fit work schedules was difficult for many, with 42.7% agreeing with this statement.

83.2% of the respondents agreed that having more money would make it easier for them to care for their children

Table 4.5b: Economic Factor of Respondents (N=89)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Management your household expenses		
I have enough money to cover all my expenses and save some	20	22.5
I have enough money to cover all my expenses but not save any	10	11.2
I have enough money to cover most of my expenses but struggle with some	28	31.5
I do not have enough money to cover all my expenses and often borrow or use credit	23	25.8
I do not have enough money to cover any of my expenses and rely on external help	8	9
Work-related responsibilities often interfere with caregiving duties		
Strongly Agree	20	22.5
Agree	32	36
Disagree	24	27
Strongly Disagree	13	14.6
Type of childcare you currently use		
Paid nanny or house help in my home	1	1.1
Grandma, sister, or other relative or friend in my home	12	13.5
I drop my child at a relative, friend, or neighbor's home	3	3.4
Creche or daycare business in the home of the childcare provider	16	18
Creche, preschool, or daycare service in a school	41	46.1
Creche, preschool, or daycare service in a church or mosque	1	1.1
I take care of my child myself always	26	29.2
Satisfied with the quality of childcare services available to you		
Strongly Agree	32	36
Agree	35	39.3
Neutral	17	19.11
Disagree	4	4.5

Strongly Disagree	1	1.1
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You faced financial challenges, in the past year, that affected your ability to provide childcare

Strongly Agree	46	51.7
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Strongly Disagree	33	37.1
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Neutral	10	11.2
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Variable	Frequency	Percentage
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Table 4.5c: Economic Factor of Respondents (N=89)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Difficulty finding childcare that fits your work schedule		
Strongly agree	16	18
Agree	22	24.7
Neutral	19	21.3
Disagree	31	34.8
Strongly disagree	1	1.1
Imagine having all the resources needed. How ideally children to be cared for on weekdays		
By me (parent)	61	68.5
Paid nanny or house help in my home	4	4.5
Creche or daycare business in the home of the childcare provider	7	7.9
Creche, preschool, or daycare service in a school	16	18
Office daycare facility	1	1.1
Having more money make it easier for you to care for your children yourself		
Strongly agree	59	66.3
Agree	15	16.9
Neutral	8	9
Disagree	7	7.9

Having stable housing make it easier to get help with childcare

Strongly agree	41	46.1
Agree	36	40.4
Neutral	9	10.1
Disagree	3	3.4

Own home, or rent

Own	5	5.6
Rent	84	94.4

In the past year, moved homes more than once or had challenges with paying rent

Yes	33	37.1
No	56	62.9

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
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Some (69%) of the paid caregivers’ reported that the financial status of a family affects the quality-of-care they observed mothers provide for their children. This influence extends to the provisions parents made for their children at the centres, with many (72.4%) respondents noting that financial limitations result in inadequate supplies, affecting children's nutrition and care. Moreover, some (62.1%) caregivers believe that a family's financial situation impacts parental involvement in their children's learning, care, and development. Regarding childcare fees, the most common fee bracket, charged by 31% of centres, is between 6,000 and 10,000 naira monthly. Despite these low fees, many (72.4%) parents face challenges in paying for childcare services, often due to delayed salaries or low business income (48.3%). To manage these challenges, a little over half (51.7%) of caregivers adopt a patient and understanding approach, while 27.5% offer flexible payment options, including instalment plans, discounts and special offers (24.1%), and financial advice (31%) . The financial strain on parents also impacts childcare centres, as about 34.5% of centres report challenges in meeting staff salary, while

20.7% face operational difficulties due to limited resources. However, 24.1% of caregivers report no significant impact of financial challenges on their operations.

Table 4.6: Effect of economic factors on childcare practices (N=29)

Variables	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Financial status of the family affecting the quality-of-care mothers give their children at your centre	Yes	20	69
	No	9	31
Financial status of the family affects the kind provisions parents make for their children at your centre	Yes	21	72.4
	No	8	27.6
Financial status of the family affects how involved the parent is in the learning, care and development of their children at your centre	Yes	18	62.1
	No	11	37.9
If you answered 'yes', please give reasons	Low quality diet and meal preparation	5	17.2
	Impact on child development	2	6.9
	Overall parental attitude	2	6.9
	Inadequate supplies/resource	6	20.6
	Current economic situation	8	27.6
	None	6	20.7
Centre charge for childcare per month	6000-10000 naira	9	31
	11000-15000 naira	5	17.2
	16000-20000 naira	7	24.1
	21,000-25,000 naira	1	3.4
	26,000-30,000 naira	1	3.4
	I don't know/none	6	20.7
Parents who use your childcare service who have challenges paying for your service	Yes	21	72.4
	No	8	27.6

Reasons for their challenges in paying	Delayed salaries/low business income	14	48.3
	Financial/ economic challenges	6	20.7
	Health issues	8	27.6
	None	1	3.4
Handling the situation	Payment flexibility such as instalment plans	8	27.5
	Patience and understanding	15	51.7
	Discount fee and extensions	6	20.1
Challenges in affording the childcare service affect you and/or operations centre	Challenges with staff salaries	10	34.5
	Limited resources for operations	6	20.7
	Difficulty in recruiting and retaining staff	1	3.4
	Low attendance due to children staying at home and this affect relationships with toddlers	5	17.2
	Not at all	7	24.1
Centre activities to support families struggling to pay	Flexible payment plans	8	27.6
	Discounts and special offers	7	24.1
	Patience, encouragement and advice on how to manage finances	9	31
	Providing free basic needs like diapers and also learning materials	1	3.4
	Nothing	4	13.8
Variables	Response	Frequency	Percentage

4.1.5. Role of Social Support Networks and Paid Childcare Services

Family members, particularly younger siblings, elder sisters, and mothers, played a significant role in providing childcare assistance. The presence of extended family, including mother-in-law and father-in-law, was also noted, suggesting a strong reliance on familial ties for childcare. About 58.4% were in agreement that grandparents provided the best care for children. Neighbors were mentioned as additional sources of support, indicating that community relationships were valued in the parenting experience. Unfortunately, many respondents lacked such strong social support networks, with 42.7% reporting no support network for caregiving. When it came to living arrangements, 74.2% of families did not live with extended family members like grandparents, aunts, or uncles, however, 25.8% of the respondents could still access these extended family members, such as grandparents, for childcare. Interestingly, although 71.9% of respondents stated that family traditions or the way they were raised did not directly influence how they raised their own children, 47.2% indicated that maintaining cultural traditions in caregiving was very important. Regarding comfort levels in discussing caregiving needs within the family, 43.8% felt comfortable doing so at all times. According to the respondents,

"My mother-in-law occasionally helps." (28 years, Primary)

"I carry him around myself." (31 years, Secondary school)

Also, regarding family support in caregiving, many (62.9%) respondents mentioned that their spouse or partner was the only available helper when needed. For families with very young children (0-3 years), almost half (49.4%) of the respondents reported that currently both parents equally shared caregiving responsibilities, however 38.2% did not agree that the responsibilities were shared equally and 11.2% of mothers handled these responsibilities alone compared to 1.1% of fathers. The analysis revealed a consensus among respondents regarding the father's role in raising children, with a strong emphasis on financial provision above active participation in childcare. However, many mothers believed that fathers should provide not only monetary support but also emotional and physical presence. This included taking children out, bathing them, and assisting with caregiving responsibilities 'when mothers were unavailable'. As stated by some of the respondents

"Daddy's role is to provide money for the family." (31 years, Secondary school)

"They should assist in taking care of the baby and bathing the baby too. (27 years, Secondary school)

When asked about the likelihood of relying on family for childcare if daycare services were unaffordable, nearly half (48.3%) were inclined to depending on the situation and 22,5% said a definite yes.

The results also revealed a widespread reluctance among respondents to leave children in the care of fathers or uncles for extended periods, primarily due to concerns over the father's skills and confidence in managing childcare, especially during challenging moments, such as when a child is crying. Many mothers believed that they were inherently better suited for caregiving, reflecting deep-seated worries about fathers' abilities and the influence of societal expectations. For example, one respondent stated, "I can't because he doesn't know what to do when the child is crying," emphasizing the perceived inadequacy of fathers. Additionally, cultural perceptions played a significant role, with another respondent noting, "Nigerian men have pride and might think of what people will say," further illustrating the complexities surrounding gender roles in parenting. While some expressed comfort in leaving their children with fathers, the overall sentiment remained cautious.

About 65.2% used paid childcare service with 46.1% of these respondents using center based daycare services, 18% using home based services and 1% hiring an in-home nanny. 18% mostly depended on unpaid childcare support from various social networks. 78.7% were less inclined to accept that cultural beliefs influenced their decision to use daycare services.

Fisher's Exact analysis showed that the type of childcare facility and the position held within these facilities significantly affect cultural influence on childcare practices. A statistically significant p-value of 0.034 shows that those using center/school-based daycare tend to have lower cultural influence, while individuals using home-based daycare display higher cultural influence. Furthermore, the significant p-value of 0.024 for position suggests that staff roles impact cultural influence: all teachers fall under the low cultural influence group, while directors and caregivers are more evenly distributed across both high and low cultural influence groups. Thus, both facility type and staff position contribute to the level of cultural influence on childcare practices.

Figure 4.1: Level of cultural Influence on childcare practices among caregivers at the Centers

Some (34.5%) of the caregiver respondents reported that mothers struggle with balancing work and childcare responsibilities, making it the most frequent challenge reported. Feeding issues followed closely behind at 24.1%. To help mothers address these challenges, nearly half (48.3%) of the caregivers provide parenting education. Caregivers also face challenges in supporting mothers. The biggest issue is resistance to change (31%), where mothers are reluctant to adopt new practices. Limited time and availability (20.7%) also hinder the support process, as well as inconsistent follow-through (13.8%). However, some caregivers (13.8%) report no challenges in their efforts to support mothers (Table 4).

Table 4.7: Childcare Challenges

Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Problems faced in caring for children at the center	Space and resources	7	24.1
	Nutrition and feeding challenges	5	17.2
	Poor parental involvement and communication	5	17.2
	Child behaviour management	7	24.1
	Operational challenges like late pickup	2	6.9
	None	3	10.3

The Caregiver-Reported Early Child Development Index (CREDI) was used to evaluate children’s development across cognitive, language, motor skills, and social-emotional domains. The Mann-Whitney U test compared CREDI scores between children in center-based and home-based daycare. Results indicated a significant difference in cognitive scores, with children in center-based care scoring higher than those in home-based daycare ($p = 0.031$). This suggests that the structured environment and interactive activities in center-based care may better support cognitive development. Although children in center-based care exhibited higher mean ranks across language, motor skills, social-emotional, and overall development domains, these differences were not statistically significant (p -values > 0.05). This implies that, for these developmental areas, home-based care with adequate support, can provide comparable support to center-based environments even within resource-limited settings. Table 1 summarizes the Mann-Whitney U test results across each development domain.

Table 4.8. Comparison of CREDI Scores between Center-Based and Home-Based Care

Domain	Mean Rank (Center-Based)	Mean Rank (Home-Based)	p-value
Cognitive	56.1	42.4	0.03
Language	55.2	43.5	>0.05
Motor Skills	54.7	44	>0.05
Social-Emotional	53.8	44.9	>0.05
Overall	55.3	43.4	>0.05

4.2. Discussion

The first objective aimed to investigate how cultural norms shape infant-toddler responsive caregiving practices within low-income urban communities in Alimosho LGA, Lagos, Nigeria. The results indicated that cultural norms significantly influence caregiving behaviors, with caregivers often adhering to traditional practices that prioritize communal values and collective child-rearing during focus group discussions and interviews, although this mildly reflected in quantitative analysis (Table 4.3 a and b). Common practice isuch as massaging the baby's body, particularly the navel, legs, and hands, was also frequently mentioned, as it is thought to promote relaxation, proper development, and aid sleep. Physical closeness, such as carrying or backing children, was also common, as many caregivers believed it provided comfort and security. Affection was not limited to physical touch; caregivers also spoke about showing love through verbal expressions especially singing, and giving gifts like snacks, toys, and new clothes. Co-sleeping was also seen as beneficial for closely monitoring the baby.

As mentioned by some of the respondents

“Yes, when he is crying, I carry him and pet him, then sing his favorite songs, ‘Baby Shark’ and ‘Mummy mummy yes papa.” (35 years, OND)

“Yes, I back her because I believe she's more comfortable.” (40 years, HND/Degree)

"We massage the baby’s body, legs, and hands because it helps them sleep well." (39 years, OND)

This finding aligns with the theoretical framework that emphasizes the importance of proximal processes in child development, as highlighted by theorists like Vygotsky and Rogoff (2023) that buttres the Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theoretical position, which argues that interactions within cultural contexts are crucial for developmental outcomes . When comparing these results with existing literature, the findings resonate with studies conducted in similar contexts. Traditional practices such as co-sleeping, baby massage, and extended family involvement in caregiving practices were prevalent and appreciated in the community of study, which was similar to the study of the Aka foragers alloparenting and Nso mothers in Cameroon, who were observed to often use physical closeness for

emotional regulation (Lavelli et al., 2019; Mesman et al., 2018). However, these practices seem to be evolving from the pre-independence collective child-rearing duties described by Akinware and Oguntuashe (2023) due to economic pressures. The findings also highlighted a tension between traditional norms and emerging practices, as a number of mothers questioned certain cultural methods (e.g., rigorous baby shaking or tossing to alleviate fear), reflecting cultural adaptation amidst urbanization and exposure to new information. However, while caregivers expressed discomfort with some traditional practices, they often adhered to practices like corporal punishment and females as sole caregivers, reflecting deeply ingrained cultural norms about discipline and gender roles (see 4.1.2 above). Ajayi and Owumi (2013) highlighted how cultural practices can suppress emotional expression and impede child development. This was unfortunately revealed in our study by the way toddlers responded with limited emotional expressions during observations (Table 4.4b), reinforcing the idea that while cultural norms can provide a framework for caregiving, they must be critically examined to ensure they promote rather than hinder child development. Again, despite the cultural emphasis on preference for communal caregiving, there was limited engagement in language-rich interactions during observation, resonating with findings from rural Burkina Faso, where caregivers undervalued interactive activities (Dumbaugh et al., 2023). Likewise the unanimous agreement during focus group discussions that the woman was a more suitable and culturally accepted infant and toddler caregiver and low ratio of male participation for the descriptive data (Table 4.1) revealed deep seated cultural biases disadvantageous to men, women and children.

The second objective of this study examines the immediate effects of culturally influenced caregiving practices on infant-toddler developmental domains within low-income urban communities. In exploring specific responsive caregiving behaviours, during focus group discussions and in depth interviews, the study categorised discussions of maternal responsive behaviours into four components: (1) contingent responding, (2) emotional-affective support, (3) support for infant foci of attention and (4) language inputs, in line with with the conceptual model for the OMCI tool, (based on a theoretical framework reported by Landry and colleagues (Landry et al., 2006) and during direct observation using the OMCI tool captured in Table 4.4a, about half (50.0%) never asked the child questions about the pictures or activities they were engaged in and many (60.0%) were never able to answer the child's questions or requests, providing little to no language stimulation. About half (50.0%) exhibited negative touch behaviors, pushing the child away or handling them roughly at two occasions at most in 5 minutes of

interaction. Additionally, some caregivers (40.0%) never expressed positive verbal statements, praising the child or conveying love and about half (45.0%) sometimes showed negative affect, sometimes displaying frustration or disengaging from the child for extended periods.

This clearly revealed in interactions, reactions and responses from the children engaged showed in Table 4.4b. Some of the children (40.0%) rarely smiled or laughed with their caregiver, indicating a poor interaction. Additionally, some (40.0%) never showed excitement and enjoyment, such as clapping. When it came to expressions of distress, a some 30.0% sometimes cried, frowned, or appeared frustrated. Lastly, 60% of children expressed very little to no enjoyment while exploring together. About 45.0% of children were rarely able to continue their activities when distracted, However, while exploring books for at least one minute, 30% often stayed engaged by looking at pictures and trying to turn pages and when it came to vocalizing or producing words, many (35%) were often able to use words or ask questions. Toddlers who initially tried to engage inactive mothers were observed to eventually give up or altogether ignore or refuse the mothers participation if and/or when she eventually attempted engaging.

These observations were clearly in contrast to mothers report to engaging in behaviors that fostered emotional bonding, secure attachment, and social skills development which were obtained is focus group discussions and in-depth-interviews.

Caregivers emphasized the effects of caregiving practices mostly in relation to physical development and long term socio-emotional outcomes which could not be measured in this study. Respondents reflected on the connections between cultural childcare practices such as bathing, feeding, and massage and child development. Some traditional practices, like tossing babies to reduce their fear of heights or using herbal baths to promote strength, were mentioned, but many respondents questioned their efficacy. However, some did recognize potential benefits.

In contrast, opinions varied regarding whether children aged 0-3 years can be overindulged from displaying responsive childcare practices, with some respondents asserting that they can be, while others believe they cannot at this age, indicating a need for nurturing rather than concern over-indulging. According to the respondents,

"I think the hot water massage helps them to relax, which I like." (34 years, Vocational training)

"I don't shout because when you shout, you are passing your fear on them." (30 years, Secondary school)

The findings underscore the significant influence of cultural norms on infant-toddler development, spanning cognitive, social-emotional, and physical domains revealed by their responses and reactions. Culturally responsive practices such as co-sleeping, baby massage, and interactive caregiving contributed to positive outcomes in areas such as physical comfort and emotional security, revealed in focus group discussions, aligning with studies in similar contexts, such as Lavelli et al. (2019), which highlighted the role of culturally proximal caregiving practices like babywearing in fostering emotional co-regulation. However, the study diverges from research in high-income settings, where cognitive stimulation and language-rich interactions are more prevalent caregiving priorities (Scherer et al., 2019). The study also highlighted limitations in language stimulation and cognitive engagement, with caregivers often prioritizing immediate physical needs over developmental enrichment. Observations revealed that while caregivers responded promptly to physical distress, they were less likely to engage in activities fostering curiosity or language development. Notably, nearly 60% of observed caregivers failed to provide adequate language stimulation, which could hinder long-term cognitive and socio-emotional growth (Table 4.4a). Quantitative findings corroborated these observations as well. Children who experienced less interactive caregiving showed greater negative emotional responsiveness and poorer engagement in activities and vice versa (Table 4.4b). Limited focus on cognitive development observed in Alimosho echoes findings from rural Burkina Faso, where talking and playing with children are undervalued (Dumbaugh et al., 2023). This suggests a broader regional trend in underemphasizing cognitive stimulation in early caregiving.

The study's hypothesis (H2)—that there is no significant association between caregiver-child interaction behaviors and child engagement—was rejected based on inferential analysis. The significant positive correlation ($r = 0.692$, $p < 0.001$) underscores the importance of responsive caregiving in shaping immediate child engagement and emotional responses (Table 4.4c). These findings validate the theoretical framework of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model, particularly the role of proximal processes in child development (Vélez-Agosto et al., 2017). Yang and Wang (2019)

noted that different cultural contexts yield distinct caregiver-child interaction styles, which can either facilitate or impede child development. Also, an unexpected finding was the dual nature of mothers caregivers beliefs and practices. While caregivers expressed knowledge and appreciation for culturally informed nurturing behaviors, such as physical closeness and rhythmic interactions, these were counterbalanced by practices potentially detrimental to child development (Table 4.4a). For example, harsh disciplinary methods, which reflect cultural norms emphasizing obedience, were still prevalent during interviews, focus group discussions and observations. Additionally, many caregivers viewed responsive caregiving as synonymous with "pampering," leading to hesitancy in employing strategies such as emotional support or verbal praise, particularly for toddlers. Another surprising trend was the caregivers' reliance on traditional beliefs to justify caregiving methods, such as using hot towels for massages to promote health or throwing infants to reduce fear of heights. While these practices reflect cultural ingenuity, they often lack alignment with evidence-based child development approaches.

Although studies have shown increasing paternal engagement in stimulation is likely to improve early child development in LMICs (Jeong et al., 2016), the findings of this study revealed limited male involvement in daily child-rearing activities and a prevailing cultural bias against male participation, particularly in caregiving for infants and toddlers. This dynamic exists despite men playing an active role in decision-making concerning their children. Such a scenario may create a lose-lose situation for all parties involved, especially as the majority of respondents in the study resided in nuclear households consisting solely of the mother, father, and children. Reduced paternal involvement in caregiving not only diminishes fathers' understanding and appreciation of early childhood development but also hampers their ability to support mothers. This lack of support may exacerbate the challenges mothers face in balancing household responsibilities, workforce participation, and contributions to household income, ultimately affecting both parents' capacity to foster cognitive and socio-emotional development in their infants and toddlers.

The third objective investigating how economic factors interact with cultural norms to shape caregiving practices in low-income urban communities, highlighted the multifaceted influence of economic instability, cultural expectations, and social dynamics on caregiving, underscoring the challenges faced by families in providing responsive care for their children. The findings revealed that limited income restricted access to quality childcare, compelling families to depend on informal paid arrangements or unpaid support networks. Even when paid childcare was accessed, financial constraints delayed

payments and limited supplies necessary for child well-being. These findings align with Gilmour's (2018) assertion that financial instability disrupts consistent caregiving and negatively impacts child development. The study interestingly revealed that economic pressures or the high usage of paid (mostly unregulated) childcare services, both unique to densely populated low-income communities, does not diminish yearnings amongst inhabitants for social support networks in childrearing borne from cultural communal living and practices. Support networks, particularly extended family, also offered a economical solution for many families. However, access to these networks has become scarce, with only 25.8% of respondents able to rely on free social network support. This decline supports Aref et al. (2024), who highlighted how urban migration and high-density living reduce the availability of family-based support, placing further strain on caregivers. The increased reliance on low cost and mostly unregulated paid childcare services, often of low quality, aligns with Oloo et al. (2023), who documented similar trends in sub-Saharan Africa.

Unfortunately, the notable trend in the erosion of communal caregiving in urban settings, where nuclear family structures dominate, also negatively impacts childcare dynamics in such low-income communities by placing greater caregiving burdens on mothers, diverging from the traditional shared caregiving model prevalent in rural communities. Although 49.4% of respondents reported sharing caregiving duties with their partners, 38.2% indicated a disproportionate burden on women, and 11.2% of mothers managed caregiving responsibilities alone compared to just 1.1% of fathers. This aligns with Ajayi and Owumi (2013), who observed that women in Nigeria often balance economic and caregiving roles, reinforcing cultural expectations that position mothers as primary nurturers. Consequently, employed mothers from the study seemed to bear the brunt of such unfavorable dynamics in the study resulting to work disruptions echoing Pilarz et al. (2022), who identified caregiving-related work interruptions as a barrier to women's economic mobility. This dual burden often forces women into informal or part-time work with lower pay and benefits, perpetuating cycles of poverty in low-income households.

In line with the fourth objective of the study, it was found that 42.7% relied on immediate family members or neighbors for childcare, reflecting the importance of social support in mitigating economic limitations. Support networks, including extended family members such as grandparents, offer a cost-effective solution for many families, as 30.3% of respondents agreed that grandparents provided the best care (Table 4.3a). This reliance on family and community for childcare aligns with traditional

caregiving norms observed in low-income communities in Nigeria, where extended family support is an integral part of daily life. However, the over-reliance on these support networks poses challenges. While family members may provide immediate childcare, they often lack the training and resources needed for high-quality early childhood education, potentially affecting children's development. This finding echoes research by Scherer et al. (2019), which highlights that unpaid support networks may lack the structure necessary to support children's cognitive and social development adequately. Thus, while unpaid support networks play a vital role, they cannot fully replace the benefits of regulated and well-resourced childcare environments.

Findings also revealed from quantitative data (Table 4.2) that in Alimosho's unregulated childcare centers, the typical child-to-caregiver ratio ranged from 1:6 to 1:10, which can significantly affect supervision quality and increase safety risks. These findings support a UNICEF (2023) report noting that unregulated childcare centers in low-income settings often lack adequate infrastructure and proper supervision, which is essential to maintaining a safe and conducive environment for young children. The study also found that, despite being paid, many caregivers in unregulated settings lacked formal training. Approximately 55.2% of caregivers had no formal childcare training, which negatively affected the quality of care provided. The study's hypothesis (H3)—that sociodemographic characteristics, such as type of childcare facility and caregiver position, are not significantly associated with cultural influences on caregiving—was rejected (Table 4.8). Inferential statistical analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between type of childcare provider and cultural caregiving preferences. The study's assessment of developmental outcomes, particularly through the Caregiver-Reported Early Child Development Index (CREDI), revealed significant disparities between children in center-based and home-based care settings. Specifically, children in center-based care scored higher in cognitive development compared to those in unregulated home-based settings, with a p-value of 0.031. This suggests that center-based environments, even if not fully regulated, may provide more structure and stimulation conducive to cognitive growth. However, for other developmental domains, such as motor skills, social-emotional development, and language, no significant differences were found between regulated and unregulated care. These findings imply that while unregulated care may meet some physical and social needs, the lack of structured, development-focused activities limits cognitive advancement. The lack of regulated, high-quality childcare options poses developmental risks, indicating a need for policies that improve childcare accessibility and quality in low-income urban

areas. These insights also underscore the need for regulatory frameworks that ensure minimum standards of care, regardless of the setting, to enhance children’s safety and developmental outcomes.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECCOMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

This study explored the interplay of cultural norms, economic factors, and caregiving practices in shaping infant-toddler development within low-income urban communities in Alimosho LGA, Lagos, Nigeria. The findings highlighted the profound influence of cultural norms, the mitigating role of economic realities, and the contributions of both social support networks and paid childcare services to responsive caregiving.

Cultural norms were found to significantly shape caregiving behaviors, with caregivers adhering to traditional practices which contributed to emotional security and physical comfort. However, limitations in language stimulation and cognitive engagement, alongside practices like corporal punishment and strict gender roles in caregiving, underscored the need to critically evaluate traditional practices to ensure they align with evidence-based approaches to child development.

The tension between deeply ingrained cultural practices and emerging caregiving behaviors reflects the community's gradual adaptation to urbanization and exposure to new information. economic factors were shown to compound caregiving challenges, with limited income restricting access to quality childcare. Social support networks and unregulated paid childcare services played critical roles in this caregiving dynamics. While paid childcare services provided some relief, the unregulated nature of these facilities often compromised care quality, particularly in cognitive stimulation and safety. The reliance on such informal support networks, though integral to the community's caregiving framework, posed challenges due to inadequate training and resources, further limiting developmental outcomes for children. Families relying on grandparents and neighbors for childcare benefited from cost-effective solutions rooted in cultural communal norms. This was found to be declining though.

The decline in traditional family-based support systems, coupled with the challenges of unregulated childcare services, highlights the need for policies that address these gaps. Notably, center-based care, despite its limitations, offered better cognitive developmental outcomes than unregulated home-based care settings.

This study provides valuable insights but has a few limitations. Its geographic and demographic scope limits generalizability to other contexts. The data captured only at one point in time, restricts understanding of long-term effects on child development. The study also mostly reflects maternal perspectives, underrepresenting the role of fathers and extended family in caregiving. Furthermore, while cognitive and emotional outcomes were assessed using the Caregiver-Reported Early Child Development Index (CREDI), other developmental aspects, such as motor skills and health, were less explored. These limitations suggest the need for future research with larger, more diverse samples, longitudinal designs, and a broader focus on family dynamics and developmental outcomes to enhance understanding of caregiving practices in low-income urban communities.

The findings have significant implications for policy and practice, particularly concerning the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and social policies aimed at improving child development outcomes and supporting caregivers. The implications of these findings are profound, particularly concerning the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Addressing financial barriers to quality childcare is critical for reducing poverty (SDG 1). By improving access to affordable, high-quality childcare services, this can support parents' participation in the workforce, reduce household stress, and enhance child developmental outcomes, ultimately contributing to poverty reduction. Promoting culturally sensitive yet evidence-based caregiving practices is essential for enhancing both emotional and cognitive well-being in early childhood aligning with SDG 3's vision for good health and well-being. Strengthening social support networks and improving childcare services can also elevate caregiving quality, ultimately enhancing the health and well-being of young children. Specifically for SDG 4 (Quality Education), investing in quality childcare services is crucial for laying the foundation for better educational outcomes. Addressing gaps in language stimulation and cognitive engagement highlights the need for early childhood education programs tailored to low-income urban contexts. These programs can foster cognitive and socio-emotional development, setting the stage for long-term academic success. For SDG 5 (Gender Equality), policies that support maternal employment and promote equitable caregiving responsibilities are critical for reducing gender disparities. Expanding access to affordable childcare can alleviate the caregiving burden on women, enabling them to participate more fully in the workforce, thereby advancing gender equality. Finally, expanding access to affordable childcare in low-income communities is crucial for bridging developmental and economic inequities which is the focus of SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities). Addressing disparities in the

accessibility and quality of childcare services can reduce developmental inequities, ensuring that all children, regardless of their socio-economic background, have the best opportunity to thrive.

5.2. Recommendations

The findings suggest several policy recommendations aimed at improving childcare quality and supporting caregivers in low-income communities:

1. Policymakers must recognize the importance of integrating cultural norms into the design and implementation of childcare programs to ensure their effectiveness and community acceptance. Culturally sensitive programs can enhance caregiver engagement and promote child development in ways that resonate with the community's values.
2. To ensure that paid childcare services provide safe, developmentally appropriate care, there is a need for regulatory oversight. This should include setting standards for caregiver training, child-to-caregiver ratios, and facility infrastructure, particularly in unregulated childcare settings.
3. Policymakers should promote community-based initiatives that revitalize traditional caregiving networks, particularly in urban settings. These initiatives can help restore the communal caregiving structures that have eroded due to urbanization, offering caregivers both practical and emotional support.
4. Given the financial pressures on low-income families, subsidized childcare services should be prioritized to make quality care more accessible. Additionally, informal caregivers, such as grandparents and extended family members, should be provided with training and resources to improve the quality of care they offer.
5. Social policies should aim to raise awareness about the importance of responsive caregiving and the benefits of structured, paid childcare services. Training programs for caregivers should incorporate culturally sensitive approaches that blend traditional caregiving practices with evidence-based child development strategies.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Interview Guide

Consent Form

I, _____, hereby grant consent for the Community Childcare Project to conduct interviews with me and capture visual content, including photographs and film footage, at _____ for the purposes outlined in the accompanying letter.

I understand that the information gathered and visual content captured may be used in project presentations, reports, and promotional materials, both in print and digital formats, related to the community childcare project. However, I trust that any identifying information about the children in my care will be kept confidential unless express permission is granted by their parents or legal guardians.

I understand that my participation in this project is voluntary, and I have the right to decline or withdraw my consent at any time. I acknowledge that my decision will not affect my relationship with the organization conducting the community childcare project or the community.

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Date Received by Community Childcare Project: _____

Signature: _____

communitychildcareproject@gmail.com || +234 810 693 2477 | 152 Akowonjo Rd, Egheda

Appendix B: Survey Instrument

Impact of Cultural Norms on Responsive Childcare Practices in Select Semi-Urban Communities in Alimosho LGA

Date: _____

Instructions: Please choose the answer that best describes your situation.

Demographic Factors:

1. What is your sex?
 - a) Male
 - b) Female
2. What is your age range?
 - a) 18-24 years old
 - b) 25-34 years old
 - c) 35-44 years old
 - d) 45-54 years old
 - e) 55+ years old
3. What is your highest level of education completed?
 - a) No formal education
 - b) Primary school
 - c) Secondary school
 - d) Vocational training
 - e) OND/Diploma
 - f) Higher education
4. What is your marital status:
 - a) Married
 - b) Living with a partner
 - c) Single
 - d) Divorced/separated
 - e) widowed
5. What is your cultural background? _____
6. How many people live in your household (including yourself)? _____
7. How many children do you currently have living with you? _____
8. How many children under the age of 4 live in your household? _____
9. What is your relationship to these children
 - a) I am their parent
 - b) I am their relative (grandparent, aunty, uncle, etc)

- c) I am their Nanny
- d) I am their older sibling (sister, step-sister, etc)
- e) I am their guardian (not related but child lives with you)
- f) Other: _____

10. Do you have a support network (friends, family, neighbors) to assist with caregiving tasks?

- a) Yes, a strong support network
- b) Yes, a moderate support network
- c) Yes, but limited support
- d) No support network

Socioeconomic Factors:

11. Do you currently have work that earns you money?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

12. Is this work outside your home?

- a) Yes, I have to leave my home to my workplace
- b) No, I work from home
- c) Sometimes I am able to work from home
- d) Not applicable

13. If you work outside the home, how many hours do you typically work per day? (include transportation time to and from work)

14. How would you describe your employment status:

- a) Employed full-time
- b) Employed part-time
- c) Self-employed
- d) Unemployed and looking for work
- e) Unemployed and not looking for work
- f) Retired
- g) Student
- h) Homemaker
- i) Other: _____

15. What do you rely on for your main income? (Choose one)

- a) Money from a job or work
- b) Money from your own business or work that you do yourself
- c) Help from the government
- d) Money from a pension or retirement plan

Appendix C: Focus Group Discussion Guide

Focus Group Discussions Guidelines

Impact of Cultural Norms on Responsive Childcare Practices in Select Semi-Urban Communities in Alimosho LGA

Date: _____ Location: _____

Instruction Guide for Conducting a Focus Group Discussion

Purpose of the Focus Group

The focus group discussion aims to explore participants' perspectives, experiences, and insights related to the research topic. This will help gather qualitative data to complement other study methods.

Preparation Phase

1. Define Objectives

Clearly outline the purpose of the discussion, ensuring all questions align with the study's goals. For example:

- Understand caregiving practices influenced by cultural norms.

- Explore the impact of economic factors on childcare decisions.

2. Select Participants

- Identify 5-15 participants who meet the inclusion criteria (e.g., parents/caregivers with children in a specific age range).
- Ensure diversity in demographics (e.g., age, education, economic status) to capture varied perspectives.

3. Arrange Venue and Materials

- Choose a comfortable, quiet, and neutral location.
- Provide seating in a circular arrangement to foster interaction.
- Prepare materials:
 - Consent forms
 - Discussion guide
 - Notebooks and pens
 - Audio/video recording devices (if applicable)
 - Refreshments (optional)

4. Assign Roles

- **Facilitator:** Leads the discussion, ensures focus, and encourages participation.
- **Note-taker/Observer:** Records key points, non-verbal cues, and group dynamics.

Conducting the Focus Group

1. Opening the Session

- **Welcome Participants:** Introduce yourself and the team.
- **State the Purpose:** Clearly explain the discussion's purpose and how their input will contribute to the study.
- **Set Ground Rules:**
 - Respect everyone's opinions.
 - One person speaks at a time.
 - Maintain confidentiality.
- **Obtain Consent:** Ensure all participants sign consent forms before proceeding.

- **Icebreaker Activity:** Use a brief, light activity to help participants feel at ease.

2. Discussion Phase

Use the discussion guide to steer the conversation, but allow for flexibility to explore emerging themes.

Questions:

Understanding Cultural Beliefs and Practices:

- How do you know when your baby needs something?
- Can you tell me about some special ways you take care of your baby based on your traditions? (e.g. method used in bathing baby, introducing solid food, etc)
- It's time for your baby to sleep, but they seem wide awake and playful. What do you do to help them settle down for sleep? At what age
- What special things do you do to help Your baby feel calm and loved?
- Who do you mostly turn to for advice on raising your children
- Sometimes older relatives might have advice on raising children. How do you decide what advice to follow for your own child?
- What do you believe is the man/father's role in raising children? At what age can you leave your child with father/uncle for 12 hours or more and why?

Exploring Specific Caregiving Behaviors:

- Tell me about a typical Saturday with your child. What are some things you do together that you both enjoy?
- Imagine your baby is fussy in the evening and won't stop crying. What do you typically do to calm them down?
- How do you handle it when your child does something you don't want them to do?
- How do you know when your baby is full after eating?
- Who else helps you care for your child? How do they show they care about the baby?

Perceptions and Impact:

- In your opinion, what makes a good mother in your culture?
- Are there any childcare practices in your culture you feel uncomfortable with?

- Do you think the way you care for your baby affects their development (learning, playing, interacting with others)?
- Your mother-in-law suggests you shouldn't pick up/comfort your baby every time they cry because it will spoil them. What would you do?
- Is there anything you would like to learn more about caring for your child?
- Is there any connection between the way babies are cared for in your culture (bathing, feeding, massage practices) and how they develop?

Appendix D: Observation Scoring Sheet

Observation of Mother–Child Interaction Record Form

Mother

#	Observation Item	Rating			
		0 (never)	1 (very few)	2 (sometimes, 3–4 times)	3 (5 or more times)
1	Positive Affect Shows positive affect for the child <i>For example</i> <i>Smiles at child, laughs with child</i> <i>Speaks in a soft tone to the child</i>				
2	Negative Affect Shows negative affect for the child <i>For example</i> <i>Shows frustration with child, frowns at child</i> <i>Disengaged from child for more than 10 seconds</i>				
	Positive Touch				

(Continues)

Infant

#	Observation Item	Rating			
		0 (never)	1 (very few, 1-2 times)	2 (sometimes, 3-4 times)	3 (Often, 5 or more times)
	Positive Affect				
13	Smiles, laughs at caregiver				
14	Shows excitement and enjoyment like clapping				
	Negative Affect				
15	Crying, frowning, frustrated				
	Remains focused				
16	Explores the book for a significant time (for at least 1 minute). For example: Looks at pictures. Tries to turn page Points to picture Verbalizes to picture				
17	Continues in spite of distractions Communication				
18	Vocalizing or producing words (12 m) uses words, joint word, comments on a picture or asks questions (24 m)				
	Mutual Enjoyment				
19	Expressing enjoyment while exploring together				

Scoring:

- A. Mother score (Observation items 1-12) _____
 B. Child score (Observation items 13-19) _____
 C. Mother plus Child Score (Observation items 1-19) _____

Instructions for scoring: Use the guide to identify the value of each rating for each observation item. Add up all the values together to obtain scores.

Observation #	Rating	Value
1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19	0	0
	1	1
	2	2
	3	3
2, 4, 6, 15	0	3
	1	2
	2	1
	3	0

Infant

#	Observation Item	Rating			
		0 (never)	1 (very few, 1-2 times)	2 (sometimes, 3-4 times)	3 (Often, 5 or more times)
	Positive Affect				
13	Smiles, laughs at caregiver				
14	Shows excitement and enjoyment like clapping				
	Negative Affect				
15	Crying, frowning, frustrated				
	Remains focused				
16	Explores the book for a significant time (for at least 1 minute). For example: Looks at picture. Tries to turn page. Points to picture. Verbalizes to picture.				
17	Continues in spite of distractions Communication				
18	Vocalizing or producing words (12 m) (use words, joins word, comments on a picture or asks questions (24 m) Mutual Enjoyment				
19	Expressing enjoyment while exploring together				

Scoring:

- A. Mother score (Observation items 1-12) _____
 B. Child score (Observation items 13-19) _____
 C. Mother plus Child Score (Observation items 1-19) _____

Instructions for scoring: Use the guide to identify the value of each rating for each observation item. Add up all the values together to obtain scores.

Observation #	Rating	Value
1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19	0	0
	1	1
	2	2
	3	3
2, 4, 6, 15	0	3
	1	2
	2	1
	3	0